

PROTECTING THE NORTH SEA: ABERDEENSHIRE

United
Kingdom

PROTECTING THE NORTH SEA: ABERDEENSHIRE

CREDITS

Citation: Conlon, S., Perry, A.L., García, S., Blanco, J., Álvarez, H. & Aguilar, R. 2019. Protecting the North Sea: Aberdeenshire. Oceana, Madrid. 80 pp.

Cover: Plumose anemones (*Metridium senile*). © OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

All photos are © OCEANA, unless otherwise stated.

Acknowledgements:

Oceana warmly thanks the crew of *MV Neptune* for their hard work and assistance during the 2017 expedition. We are also grateful to: JNCC, particularly Rachel Bower and Becky Hitchen, who participated in the Aberdeenshire surveys and contributed to their success; Michael McLeod (Marine Scotland) for his valuable input on priority survey areas in Scottish waters; Flora Kent (Scottish Natural Heritage), who kindly advised us on potential sampling sites; Clare Greathead (Marine Scotland Science), for her input on vulnerable ecosystems; and Calum Duncan (Marine Conservation Society) who generously shared his knowledge of Scottish marine protection.

This project was made possible thanks to the generous support of the Dutch Postcode Lottery.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY, 4

INTRODUCTION, 5

DESCRIPTION OF THE AREA, 7

- Bathymetry and substrate, 8
- Known ecological features of interest, 9
- Previous surveys, 13
- Threats, 16
- Current management measures, 21
- Previous conservation proposals, 23

OCEANA SURVEYS, 26

- Methods, 27
 - Visual surveys (ROV and SCUBA), 27
 - Infaunal sampling, 28
 - Oceanographic parameters, 29
- Results, 29
 - Oceanographic parameters, 29
 - Community types and species, 31
 - Features of conservation interest, 40
 - Threatened and protected species, 40
 - Threatened and protected habitats, 41
 - Species of commercial interest and essential fish habitat, 46
 - Observed impacts, 50

PROPOSAL FOR PROTECTION, 51

REFERENCES, 56

ANNEX: RECORDED TAXA, 63

The sea surrounding Aberdeenshire is home to a rich diversity of seabed ecosystems, ranging from kelp forests along the coast to burrowed mud within the Southern Trench, a deep seabed incision that is both geologically and ecologically important. The value of the Southern Trench as a biodiversity hotspot has been recognised by the Scottish government, which proposed the creation of the *Southern Trench* Nature Conservation Marine Protected Area (NCMPA) to protect four biodiversity features (burrowed mud, fronts, minke whale, and shelf deeps) and two geodiversity features (Quaternary of Scotland and submarine mass movement). However, it is not yet known whether the site will in fact be designated, and protection of benthic ecosystems in the Aberdeenshire area at present is limited.

In 2017, Oceana carried out a research expedition in the waters of Aberdeenshire, to gather further information about the area's benthic species and communities. Surveys were conducted mainly through low-impact visual means (filming via a remotely operated vehicle and by professional divers) and were complemented with seabed grab sampling of sediments and infauna. Locations surveyed included unprotected areas, points within the area's three existing marine protected areas (none of which protect seabed ecosystems), and the proposed *Southern Trench* NCMPA. In total, Oceana documented 481 taxa (351 to the species level), in association with 14 habitat types. Among the marine features recorded were 16 species and seven habitat types that are considered priorities for conservation under Scottish or international frameworks. Key findings included reefs and other aggregations formed by ross worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*), kelp forests, submerged caves, and sea pen and burrowing megafauna communities.

On the basis of its findings, Oceana strongly supports the designation of the *Southern Trench* NCMPA, and encourages the Scottish government to grant formal protection to other features found within the site. In particular, the Aberdeenshire area appears to be important for ross worm (*S. spinulosa*) reefs, both within the proposed *Southern Trench* site and beyond its southern boundary. Oceana urges the Scottish authorities to extend the site boundaries to encompass these vulnerable habitats, to carry out further studies to assess the extent and condition of *S. spinulosa* reefs, and to develop appropriate measures of protection. Extending the boundary of the *Southern Trench* would have the added benefit of safeguarding other features of conservation importance in the same area, including kelp forests, submerged caves, and seven species that are considered Priority Marine Features in Scottish waters.

The waters of the North Sea surrounding Aberdeenshire (Figure 1) are characterised by a wide range of geological and geomorphological features that, in turn, host a diverse array of marine biotypes and species. One area of particular interest is the Southern Trench, located along the south coast of the Moray Firth. The origin of this large-scale seabed incision is still contentious, but it is thought to have been formed from at least two fluvial erosion events, and as such is important for increasing our understanding of ice sheet drainage in this area.¹ With an approximate length of 120 km and maximum depths of 250 m, it is one of the largest enclosed glacial seabed basins mapped in Scottish waters.¹ In addition to its geodiversity significance, it is considered ecologically important due to the occurrence of biodiversity features that include burrowed mud, fronts, shelf deeps, and minke whales. On the basis of these features, it was identified as a potential candidate for protection in 2012 and formally proposed as a Scottish Nature Conservation Marine Protected Area (NCMPA) in 2019. Although benthic communities in the area outside of the Southern Trench have been less well studied, the reef-forming polychaete *Sabellaria spinulosa* has been documented from some locations, on mixed sediment (see *Known ecological features of interest*). Additionally, there are extensive areas of burrowed mud, particularly in the Southern Trench, with associated communities that include burrowing megafauna such as Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and sea pens.²

Kelp forest (*Laminaria ochroleuca* and *L. hyperborea*).
© OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

The seas off Aberdeenshire are also subject to intense fishing activity, oil and gas exploration, and shipping traffic. Due to the presence of commercially important Norway lobster, burrowed mud areas are a particular target for the fishing industry. The fisheries associated with Norway lobster can have a detrimental influence on muddy habitats and their associated communities.^{3,4,5} Similarly, biogenic reefs formed by *S. spinulosa* are also highly vulnerable to damage as a result of trawling or dredging.⁶

In order to preserve the biodiversity and improve the state of health of Scottish waters, it is important to increase our understanding of the benthic communities that they host, especially in areas threatened by human activity. Oceana conducted biological research surveys in the waters of Aberdeenshire in 2017, to characterise the benthic species, communities, and habitats of the area. These surveys were part of a research expedition carried out across the waters of five North Sea countries, which aimed to gather critical data for improving the existing network of North Sea marine protected areas. The findings of Oceana's surveys are presented here, in the broader context of the marine biodiversity of the area, the threats it faces, and the implications for its protection.

Figure 1. Location of Aberdeenshire survey area. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute.⁹

DESCRIPTION OF THE AREA

The physical environment of the Aberdeenshire area has been shaped mostly by geological and glacial processes.¹⁰ This combination of drivers has resulted in a relatively flat seabed, with the exception of a deep area, the Southern Trench, located along the south coast of the Moray Firth between the coastal ports of Banff and Fraserburgh (Figure 2). This trench is thought to have been formed by at least two glacial erosive events from different directions,¹¹ although its formation is still under debate. The trench reaches depths of 244 m below sea level, with slopes ranging from as little as 2° to greater than 50°.^{1,10} This deep area is of particular interest due to the irregular morphology of the trench, making it the most topographically complex region of the Moray Firth, and one of the deepest points in Scottish North Sea waters.¹²

Figure 2. Detailed bathymetry of the Aberdeenshire survey area. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute.⁹

Sediments in the North Sea derive from the Holocene epoch and their distribution reflects the glacial history and hydrodynamic processes in the area.¹³ In the Aberdeenshire area, the dominant substrate type is sand and coarse sand, with interspersed areas of mixed sediment, rocks and other hard substrata closer to the coastline (Figure 3). In deeper, offshore waters, finer silts and muds (such as sandy mud to muddy sand) are present, particularly in the Southern Trench area. In the deepest points of the Southern Trench, the substrate is characterised by fine mud. In contrast, shallower sandy areas along the eastern coast of Aberdeenshire are characterised by sand waves with average wave lengths of 200 m and heights reaching 17 m.¹⁰

Figure 3. Substrate types and bathymetry of the Aberdeenshire survey area. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute.⁹

KNOWN ECOLOGICAL FEATURES OF INTEREST

The complex bathymetry and heterogeneity of the seafloor substrates in the waters off Aberdeenshire contribute to a diverse array of habitats and thus ecological features of interest. The Aberdeenshire survey area is known to host muddy habitats that support sea pen and burrowing megafauna communities. The reef-forming polychaete known as ross

worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*) has also been recorded in sandy and gravelly regions, with reef formations in some sites. Along the coastline, macroalgal forests have been documented on both the north and east coasts of Aberdeenshire, within the survey area. Finally, a frontal system in the Moray Firth represents an area of increased chlorophyll levels and a hotspot for marine mammals. Each of these features is described in more detail below.

Muddy habitats are extensive in the North Sea, particularly in Scottish waters, and in some areas are home to various species of sea pens.^{2,14} Burrowing megafauna associated with such habitats can include Norway lobster (*N. norvegicus*), North Sea tube anemone (*Cerianthus lloydii*), and fireworks anemone (*Pachycerianthus multiplicatus*).¹⁴ In fine sediment areas, the expected fauna includes phosphorescent sea pen (*Pennatula phosphorea*), crustaceans such as common hermit crab (*Pagurus bernhardus*) and gastropods such as slender colus (*Colus gracilis*).¹³

Edible crab (*Cancer pagurus*) and ascidians (*Clavelina lepadiformis*).
© OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

Within the Southern Trench specifically, the biotype burrowed mud has been repeatedly reported.¹⁵ Burrowed mud communities are expected to occur more broadly in the survey area due to the presence of muddy seabeds, and also the occurrence of Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and sea pens, which have been documented in previous studies and fisheries surveys.² Sea pens are considered an indicator of

the quality of mud habitats, due to their sensitivity to demersal fishing impacts.¹⁶ The distributions of three sea pen species in Scottish waters, *Virgularia mirabilis*, *P. phosphorea* and *Funiculina quadrangularis* have been determined using *N. norvegicus* stock assessment video survey data.² During this analysis, both *V. mirabilis* and *P. phosphorea* sea pens were frequently observed in the Southern Trench area.

A study conducted in 2015 by Marine Scotland Science (MSS) and Scottish Natural Heritage (SNH)¹⁷ documented populations of *N. norvegicus* and *P. phosphorea* on deep sandy mud (93-94 m), in the northwestern corner of the Southern Trench. The northern part of the Southern Trench was dominated by muddy sand, which was home to a burrowing megafauna community that included *N. norvegicus* and *P. phosphorea*. In 2017, additional surveys in the area further documented muddy bottoms, with burrows likely made by *N. norvegicus* and *Calocaris macandreae*, and frequent observations of *P. phosphorea*.¹⁸

Another known feature of interest in the waters off Aberdeenshire are biogenic reefs formed by ross worm (*S. spinulosa*). *S. spinulosa* reefs are associated with faunal levels of abundance five times higher than surrounding sedimentary habitats.¹⁹ Such reefs have the potential to affect the topographic relief of soft sediment zones; this habitat modification in areas of otherwise little topographic relief can affect the soft sediment communities present.²⁰

Various recent studies have documented the presence of this habitat type in the eastern arm of the proposed *Southern Trench* MPA. Research on *Southern Trench* habitats in 2011 found low numbers of ross worm tubes (i.e., 1-4 tubes) in grab samples at three locations, and nearly 200 tubes in a sample from the eastern part of the trench.²¹ A 2013 survey conducted for Statoil documented high abundances of *S. spinulosa* in the eastern part of the proposed MPA, extending into waters further to the east.²² *S. spinulosa* coverage was as high as 85% in some of the sites areas surveyed, and reef habitats extended over areas of up to 4,015,865 m².²² Additional *S. spinulosa* reefs and tubes were observed during later research by SNH and Cefas, in areas characterised by tide-rippled medium sand, and also in the eastern arm of the proposed *Southern Trench* MPA.^{17,23} These waters experience elevated tidal currents that favour the development of ross worm on bedrock, boulders and cobbles.¹⁷ The importance of the south-eastern arm of *Southern Trench* for *S. spinulosa* was further confirmed through more recent surveys carried out by the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC) and MSS in collaboration with SNH. *S. spinulosa* reefs were widely recorded during inshore surveys, and consolidated material forming dense encrustations, probably from *Sabellaria* activity, was abundant in deeper waters.¹⁸ Species that are considered Priority Marine Features (PMFs)²⁴ were also recorded during some of these surveys, such as juveniles of anglerfish (*Lophius piscatorius*) and ling (cf. *Molva molva*).

Kelp forests often dominate the rocky coasts of cold-water marine habitats and are considered to be one of the most diverse and productive ecosystems in the world.^{25,26,27} They develop on shallow rocky shores where light and oceanographic conditions allow the development, growth and persistence of populations.²⁶ Kelp forests provide a three-dimensional habitat in coastal waters for a diverse array of marine organisms.³⁰ For example, tangle (*L. hyperborea*) creates a large and heterogeneous habitat owing to its height (1-2 m), and can host a large number of species, often in high densities.²⁸ Kelp forests in the UK provide habitat for invertebrates and nursery habitat for fishes such as cod (*Gadus morhua*) and pollack (*Pollachius pollachius*).³⁰ They also represent feeding grounds for fish species including *Labrus bergylta* and *Ctenolabrus rupestris*.²⁹ In the Aberdeenshire survey area, documented kelp species include *Alaria esculenta*, *Laminaria digitata*, *L. hyperborea* and *Saccharina latissima*.^{30,31}

Additionally, another known feature of interest in the survey area is the frontal system in the Moray Firth. Fronts are narrow zones with steep gradients in temperature, salinity, density, turbidity and ocean colour.³² In 2013, this system was identified by detecting chlorophyll front hotspots using satellite ocean colour data.³³ The front appeared to correspond to a narrow, shallow inner shelf, which indicated that it may be associated with enhanced tidal mixing.³³ Marine mammals are associated with oceanic fronts, and the Southern Trench is characterised by higher-than average predicted densities of minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*).³⁴ Sightings of minke whales increase in the outer Moray Firth during front periods when phytoplankton biomass is at its greatest.³⁵ Other cetaceans found in the outer southern Moray Firth area include bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*), harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*), killer whale (*Orcinus orca*), long-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala melas*), humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*), and Atlantic white-sided dolphin (*Lagenorhynchus acutus*).³⁶

Beyond specific features, the waters of Aberdeenshire are also known to provide habitat for a wide range of commercial species, some of which have spawning and/or nursery grounds in the area. Such species include sandeels (Ammodytidae), herring (*Clupea harengus*), cod (*Gadus morhua*), lemon sole (*Microstomus kitt*), Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*), and plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*).^{37,38} The habitats that they rely upon for growth or spawning (along with other important habitats such as feeding grounds and migratory corridors) are known as essential fish habitats (EFH), because of the critical role that they play during species' life cycles.³⁹

The diverse array of species that use Aberdeenshire as spawning and nursery grounds could be due to the heterogeneity of the seafloor substrate and associated habitat types in the area. Additionally, the presence of a frontal system in the survey area may influence the distribution of spawning sites and nursery grounds. Frontal systems represent a

boundary between two water masses and therefore can be characterised by steep horizontal gradients in both biological and physical properties.⁴⁰ As a result, fronts have the potential to locally retain larvae that float in the water column, thereby limiting larval dispersal.⁴⁰

Plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*).
© OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

PREVIOUS SURVEYS

Since the first large-scale survey of the North Sea in 1923,⁴¹ the waters of Aberdeenshire have been studied extensively for geological, biological, and industrial interests (Table 1). Various academic, government, and industrial research bodies have made efforts to better understand the physical nature of the seabed, as well as benthic community composition in Aberdeenshire waters (Table 1).

Geophysical surveys have been conducted in the Oceana survey area, with particular attention having been paid to the Southern Trench. Detailed surveys were made along a section of the Southern Trench for the Strategic Environment Assessment Area 5 (SEA Area 5).¹¹ Data were obtained on seabed superficial geology and geological processes using multibeam bathymetry, side-scan sonar, seismic reflection profiles, seafloor photographs and samples.¹¹ Additional surveys have been conducted for the oil and gas industry and for potential wind farm installation sites.^{22,42}

In order to improve knowledge of the benthos associated with this unique area, major UK research bodies have studied seabed communities across a range of depths. For example, MSS has made efforts to characterise the Scottish marine benthos in the Moray Firth using *Nephrops* survey video data and reported burrowed mud habitats with three species of sea pens.^{2,43} MMT conducted marine geophysical research using video data and grab samples and identified areas of 'bedrock reef' and 'stony reefs', as well as aggregations of ross worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*).²² SNH was the first group to thoroughly examine both infaunal and epifaunal benthic communities in the Southern Trench using drop-down video camera footage and grab samples, identifying eight habitat biotypes.²¹ Multiple surveys carried out by SNH during the last decade have revealed locations with burrowed muddy bottoms and of habitat formed by *S. spinulosa* (see *Known ecological features of interest*).

Table 1. Major benthic biological and geological research studies carried out in the survey area.

Year of Survey	Group	Purpose of Survey	References
1922-1925	Fishery Board for Scotland	First large-scale survey of the northern North Sea. Qualitative documentation of benthic species using grab sampler.	Stephen, 1923, ⁴¹ 1933, ⁴⁴ 1934 ⁴⁵
1958	Aberdeen Marine Laboratory	Study of the benthos of fishing grounds off the east coast of Scotland, Aberdeen Bay, St Andrews Bay and the Smith Bank in the Moray Firth.	McIntyre, 1958 ⁴⁶
1975-1992	United Kingdom Offshore Operators Association	Numerous seabed surveys conducted for the oil and gas industry to provide information on localised impacts of offshore installations.	Kingston & Harries, 2000 ⁴²
1980-1985	Scottish Department of Agriculture and Fisheries, International Council for the Exploration of the Seas	Survey of the entire North Sea benthos to determine species biodiversity and abundance.	Eleftheriou & Basford, 1989; ⁴⁷ Heip <i>et al.</i> , 1990, ⁴⁸ 1992; ⁴⁹ Künitzer <i>et al.</i> , 1992; ⁵⁰ Duineveld <i>et al.</i> , 1991 ⁵¹
1982	MAFF/Luton College	Surveys of the epifauna of the North Sea using a camera attached to a trawl during demersal fish surveys.	Dyer <i>et al.</i> , 1982, ⁵² 1983; ⁵³ Cranmer 1985 ⁵⁴
1983-present	English and Scottish Groundfish Surveys	Annual demersal fish surveys using trawls.	ICES, 2019 ⁵⁵
1986	Delta Institute for Hydrobiological Research	Synoptic benthic survey across North Sea. 171 sample sites were surveyed using a Van Veen grab, concentrating on copepod communities.	Huys <i>et al.</i> , 1990, 1992 ^{56,57}

1999	Cefas	Biological survey of epibenthic species using a small beam trawl across various sites in the North Sea.	Jennings <i>et al.</i> , 1999 ⁵⁸
2001-2003	Marine Scotland Science	Determined distributions of three sea pen species, using <i>Nephrops norvegicus</i> stock assessment videos.	Greathead <i>et al.</i> , 2007 ²
2003	British Geological Survey, Department of Trade and Industry	Detailed surveys along a section of the Southern Trench for the Strategic Environment Assessment area 5 (SEA Area 5). Data obtained on seabed superficial geology and geological processes using multibeam bathymetry, side scan sonar, seismic reflection profiles, seafloor photographs and samples. Comprised both geological and biological sampling.	Holmes <i>et al.</i> , 2004 ¹¹
2008-2010	Marine Scotland Science	Analysed sea pen abundance, using <i>Nephrops</i> stock assessment videos.	Allan <i>et al.</i> , 2012 ⁴³
2010-2011	SEA/Marine Scotland	Shelf deeps of Southern Trench mapped during multibeam surveys.	Unpublished (see SNH, 2014) ⁵⁹
2011	British Geological Survey and Scottish Natural Heritage	Multibeam surveys adjacent to the survey area SEA5 (see above).	Hirst <i>et al.</i> , 2012 ²¹
2011	Heriot Watt University, Scottish Natural Heritage and Marine Scotland Science	Biological surveys of the Southern Trench, using drop-down video and grabs.	Hirst <i>et al.</i> , 2012 ²¹
2013	MMT	Marine geophysical seabed and environmental surveys around the then-proposed Hywind Offshore Wind farm site, off the east coast of Scotland. Environmental surveys comprised 34 sampling sites and 6 video transects.	Statoil Environmental Survey report ²²
2015	Scottish Natural Heritage and Cefas	Investigation of the distribution of protected features in the <i>Southern Trench</i> MPA proposal, using video data and grab sampling.	Moore, 2017 ¹⁷ ; Axelsson <i>et al.</i> , 2017 ²³
2015-2018	Scottish Natural Heritage/Marine Scotland Science and JNCC/Marine Scotland Science	Research to improve knowledge of species and habitats through analysis of seabed videos and still images collected during monitoring and research cruises.	Moore, 2019 ¹⁸

The main threats to marine biodiversity in the Aberdeenshire area originate from anthropogenic activities (Figure 4). These threats include commercial fishing, oil and gas exploitation (e.g., platforms and pipelines), shipping traffic, wind farm installations, and pollution.

Fisheries represent a major industry in Scottish waters. Within the Oceana survey area, there is widespread fishing activity using dredges, harvesting machines, seine nets, traps and trawls (Table 2) to capture both pelagic and demersal species. Over 54 species are commercially fished in Aberdeenshire waters (Table 2) including crustaceans, molluscs, gadoids, and rays. In terms of total catches by weight, the fishery for scallop (*Pecten maximus*) is the greatest (with 1226 tonnes landed in the southeast part of the survey site in 2016). *Scomber scombrus*, *Loligo* spp. and *Nephrops norvegicus* are also among the most significant fisheries by weight. Offshore sites (in the eastern part of the survey area) have a greater diversity of species caught compared to nearshore coastal fisheries, potentially owing to the high fishing effort reported from these offshore sites (Table 2).

Table 2. Effort and landing data for commercial species for UK vessels over 10 m in length. Data were obtained from ICES fishing effort data sets for 2016.^{63,64,65}

	ICES Statistical Rectangle					
	42E7	42E8	43E7	43E8	44E7	44E8
Area	SW survey area, east coast of Scotland	SE survey area	Aberdeen coast	Offshore Aberdeen	NW survey site, Moray Firth	NE survey area, offshore Peterhead
Effort (days) by UK vessels >10 m length. Annual total	1062	674	130	589	2248	1424
Gear type	Dredges, Harvesting machines, Traps, Trawls	Dredges, Harvesting machines, Seine nets, Trawls	Dredges, Traps, Trawls	Dredges, Harvesting machines, Seine nets, Traps, Trawls	Dredges, Harvesting machines, Seine nets, Traps, Trawls	Dredges, Harvesting machines, Seine nets, Traps, Trawls
Quantity of species landed (tonnes)						
<i>Anarhichas lupus</i>	-	-	-	0	0	0
Brachyura	0	-	-	-	-	0

<i>Brosme brosme</i>	-	-	-	1	0	0
<i>Buccinum undatum</i>	10	-	0	0	1	0
<i>Cancer pagurus</i>	236	5	58	167	335	380
<i>Carcinus maenas</i>	1	-	-	1	0	1
<i>Chelidonichthys cuculus</i>	-	-	-	0	1	2
<i>Clupea harengus</i>	1	0	-	97	2	-
<i>Conger conger</i>	-	-	-	-	0	0
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	-	-	-	-	0	-
<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	-	-	-	0	2	8
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	1	0	-	4	9	11
Galatheidae	-	-	-	-	0	-
<i>Glyptocephalus cynoglossus</i>	0	0	-	0	8	6
<i>Hippoglossoides platessoides</i>	-	-	-	-	0	-
<i>Hippoglossus hippoglossus</i>	0	0	-	0	2	1
<i>Homarus gammarus</i>	129	7	6	17	25	31
Labridae	-	-	-	-	0	-
<i>Lepidorhombus</i> spp.	-	-	-	0	1	1
<i>Leucoraja naevus</i>	-	0	-	-	3	3
<i>Limanda limanda</i>	-	-	-	-	4	0
<i>Loligo</i> spp.	0	6	0	0	550	62
Lophiidae	0	0	-	4	47	67
<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i>	0	4	-	25	233	215
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	-	0	-	2	15	33
<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	-	-	-	1	2	2
<i>Microstomus kitt</i>	0	0	-	0	6	6
<i>Molva molva</i>	0	-	-	-	2	3
<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	-	0	-	0	0	0
<i>Mya arenaria</i>	0	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Necora puber</i>	60	3	2	17	37	39
<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	95	2	-	7	513	113

Octopodidae	-	-	-	-	2	0
<i>Palaemon serratus</i>	3	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Palinurus</i> spp.	-	-	-	-	-	0
<i>Pecten maximus</i>	317	1226	4	640	160	753
<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0
<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i>	0	0	-	2	34	19
<i>Pollachius pollachius</i>	-	-	-	0	0	0
<i>Pollachius virens</i>	-	0	-	-	2	4
<i>Psetta maxima</i>	0	-	-	0	0	0
<i>Raja clavata</i>	-	-	-	0	4	0
<i>Raja montagui</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0
<i>Raja</i> spp.	-	-	-	-	0	-
<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	20	1	3	43	147	969
<i>Scophthalmus rhombus</i>	-	-	-	0	0	0
<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	-	-	-	-	31	5
<i>Sebastes</i> spp.	0	-	-	-	-	-
Sepiidae, Sepiolidae	-	-	-	-	0	0
<i>Solea solea</i>	-	-	-	-	0	-
<i>Solen</i> spp.	0	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	-	-	-	-	2	-
Squalidae, Scyliorhinidae	-	-	-	-	0	-
Triglidae	-	-	-	-	0	1

Various fishing gears used in the waters of Aberdeenshire are destructive and can have profound impacts on the seafloor. Demersal fishing activities such as dredging (used for scallop fisheries) and trawling (used for infaunal and epifaunal species) are associated with habitat loss and damage and with the capture of non-target organisms, altering benthic community structure.^{3,60,61} Traps and pots are also used in Scottish waters, to capture crustaceans such as *Cancer pagurus*, *Homarus gammarus* and *N. norvegicus*. Pots and traps are less destructive than mobile fishing gear,⁶² although lost pots and traps have the potential to continue to capture benthic organisms, especially if there is still bait inside: a phenomenon known as 'ghost-fishing'.

Offshore oil and gas exploitation is another major industry in the North Sea that poses multiple threats to benthic communities.^{66,67,68} Scotland is considered to be the largest producer of oil in Europe, and there are numerous wells and hydrocarbon fields within and in close proximity to the Aberdeenshire survey area (Figure 4). The St Fergus terminal on the east coast of Scotland is the largest single gas importing facility in the UK, receiving nine gas pipelines;¹⁰ to the north of Aberdeen, Cruden Bay receives oil from the Forties pipeline system. The presence of such pipelines can also cause habitat loss, due to physical disturbance of seabed substrata.

Benthic communities are also at risk from pollutants released from oil platform operations and ships. Exposure to such stressors can lead to a reduction in species abundance and diversity and an increase in opportunistic species.^{67,69} During 2014, there were a total of 748 accidental discharges from vessels and releases from offshore oil and gas installations in the UK.⁷⁰ On the eastern coast of Scotland, 18 oil spill incidents were reported, 14 of which occurred in ports and harbours, three in the open sea and one on a beach.⁷⁰

Figure 4. Oil fields, pipeline, cables and wind farm development sites in the survey area. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ Oil and Gas Authority,⁷¹ TeleGeography,⁷² The Crown Estate,⁷³ and 4c Offshore.⁷⁴

Trawler off the coast of Fraserburgh.
© OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

Along the east coast of Scotland are numerous harbours, many of which require occasional dredging to maintain navigable depths. The areas with the highest density of shipping traffic are coastal areas around Peterhead.¹⁰ The dredge spoils from navigational dredging are disposed of around the east coast of Scotland and along the coast of the Moray Firth. There are a total of five open waste disposal sites within the survey area,⁷⁵ and five closed disposal sites, one off the coast of Stonehaven and four off the coast of Peterhead.⁷⁶ Aberdeen and Peterhead each have major ports for both oil and gas, and for fishing vessels. Various smaller harbours are also dotted along the coast of the Aberdeenshire survey area.

Additionally, the *Hywind Scotland* floating offshore wind farm is located 25 km offshore from Peterhead, with the cable landing point in Peterhead.⁷⁴ The world's first floating commercial wind farm, it began supplying electricity to Scotland in late 2017. The wind farm consists of five floating turbines anchored to the seabed, each with a connection to an export cable. Prior to the development of this wind farm, an environmental survey conducted by MMT for Statoil revealed a *Sabellaria spinulosa* reef along the export cable route, and extensive *S. spinulosa* reefs within the turbine site area that were found to have higher levels of biodiversity than sites lacking *S. spinulosa*.²² Further wind farms are being developed off the coast of Aberdeen, with another wind farm also fully commissioned, *European Offshore Wind Deployment Centre*.⁷⁴ Additionally, *Kincardine Offshore Windfarm* is under construction, 15 km southeast of the Aberdeen coast.⁷⁴ A development zone for wind farms (named E3) partially overlaps with the survey site,

but it is 'subject to high levels of ornithological constraints' and encompasses known spawning area for some species, so development of wind farms within the zone will depend on science to reduce environmental risks.⁷⁷ The impacts of renewable energy and power cables can affect sediment or water quality, which may impact benthic communities by displacing or attracting species.^{78,79} Disturbance of the seabed during construction and operation can cause habitat damage directly or indirectly, through increased suspended sediment and turbidity, which poses a particular risk to benthic filter-feeding organisms.⁷⁸ Marine mammals can be sensitive to noise created by exploration and construction activities, which may cause displacement or act as a barrier to species movement.^{80,81,82}

Another significant and growing threat is marine debris. It has been estimated that 4.8-12.7 million tonnes of litter enter the oceans each year;⁸³ the North Sea alone has a mean litter abundance of 16.8 litter items per km², the majority of which are plastic.⁸⁴ Large plastics can pose a threat to marine organisms via entanglement, whereas marine organisms can ingest smaller plastics such as microplastics,⁸⁵ which have been steadily increasing in the oceans over past decades.⁸⁶ Microplastics can originate from the direct release of plastic particles and also as a result of the fragmentation of larger plastic particles.⁸⁶ A study in the North Sea sampled seven commercially important fish species, and detected microplastic in five of them (i.e., cod, herring, horse mackerel, whiting and haddock); within each of those species, the percentage of individual fish containing plastics ranged from 1-13%.⁸⁵

CURRENT MANAGEMENT MEASURES

The Oceana survey area encompasses three sites that are designated as Special Protection Areas (SPAs), overlaps with two fisheries closures, and is near to two offshore Nature Conservation MPAs (NCMPAs) (Table 3; Figure 5). The SPAs were designated for the protection of seabird breeding sites along the coast; the fisheries closures target the recovery of sandeel (*Ammodytidae*) and Norway pout (*Trisopterus esmarkii*) populations. To the east of the survey area, the offshore *Turbot Bank* NCMPA was designated for the protection of sandeel, and while the *Firth of Forth Banks Complex* NCMPA was created to protect ocean quahog (*Arctica islandica*), among other features (see Figure 5, which shows two of its three polygons). The designation of MPAs in Aberdeenshire has remained relatively stagnant, with most of the areas having been designated in the 1990s, and the two NCMPAs in 2014.

Table 3. Current spatial management measures in the survey area and vicinity.

Management measure	Details
<i>Fowlsheugh SPA</i>	Originally designated in 1992, under the EU Birds Directive. During the breeding season, the area regularly supports 170 000 seabirds, including: razorbill (<i>Alca torda</i>), herring gull (<i>Larus argentatus</i>), fulmar (<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>), guillemot (<i>Uria aalge</i>), and kittiwake (<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>). ⁸⁷
<i>Troup, Pennan and Lion's Heads SPA</i>	Originally designated in 1997, under the EU Birds Directive. During the breeding season, the area regularly supports 150 000 seabirds, including: guillemot (<i>Uria aalge</i>), razorbill (<i>Alca torda</i>), fulmar (<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>), herring gull (<i>Larus argentatus</i>), kittiwake (<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>). ⁸⁷
<i>Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast SPA</i>	Originally designated in 1998, under the EU Birds Directive. During the breeding season, the area regularly supports 95 000 seabirds, including: guillemot (<i>Uria aalge</i>), kittiwake (<i>Rissa tridactyla</i>), herring gull (<i>Larus argentatus</i>), shag (<i>Phalacrocorax aristotelis</i>) and fulmar (<i>Fulmarus glacialis</i>). ⁸⁷
Norway pout box	Designated in 1977. Norway pout fishing prohibited year-round using towed gear with a mesh size less than 32 mm. This area is closed with the intention of protecting juvenile gadoids. ⁸⁸
Northwestern North Sea Sandeel Fishery Closure	Designated in 2000. Year-round closure on sandeel fishing except for a commercial monitoring fishery with a total allowable catch limit. ⁸⁹
<i>Turbot Bank NCMPA (outside survey area)</i>	Designated in 2014, because of its importance for sandeels, particularly Raitt's sandeel (<i>Ammodytes marinus</i>). The site contains the type of sandy sediment with low silt and clay components that sandeels prefer. ⁹⁰
<i>Firth of Forth Banks Complex NCMPA (outside survey area)</i>	Designated in 2014. The site was designated to protect both biodiversity and geodiversity features, such as ocean quahog (<i>Arctica islandica</i>) aggregations, offshore subtidal sands and gravels, shelf banks and mounds, and Quaternary of Scotland – moraines. ⁹¹

Figure 5. Current spatial management measures in the area, including SPAs, sandeel and Norway pout fisheries closures, and NCMPAs. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁹ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ SNH,⁹² Wright *et al.* (1998).⁹³

PREVIOUS CONSERVATION PROPOSALS

Following the enactment of the Marine (Scotland) Act 2010,⁹⁴ the process began to identify, propose, and designate Nature Conservation MPAs (NCMPAs) in Scottish waters. These MPAs are intended to conserve marine biodiversity (both species and habitats) and geodiversity (features of geological or geomorphological interest).

In 2012, as part of this process, the Whale and Dolphin Conservation Society, the Hebridean Whale and Dolphin Trust, and the Cetacean Research and Rescue Unit proposed two potential areas for protection that overlap with the Oceana survey area (Figure 6).⁹⁵ The first of these areas encompassed part of the Southern Trench, and was proposed for the protection of minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*); the second area, along the east coast of Aberdeenshire, was put forward for the conservation of white-beaked dolphin (*Lagenorhynchus albirostris*).⁹⁵

While the proposal for the latter area did not advance, the former contributed to the identification of the Southern Trench as an MPA search location, for which further assessment was required because the existing evidence was considered to be insufficient for making a full proposal.⁹⁶ The *Southern Trench* MPA search location was considered to be of interest for an array of Scottish MPA search features,⁹⁷ including both biodiversity features (i.e., burrowed mud, fronts, shelf deeps, minke whale, and white-beaked dolphin) and geodiversity features (i.e., Quaternary of Scotland – subglacial tunnel valleys and moraines; and submarine mass movement – slide scars).⁵⁹ The search area lay primarily in territorial (i.e., nearshore) waters, encompassing the trench and roughly following the 12 nm limit. It also overlapped with the marine part of the *Troup, Pennan and Lion's Head* SPA (see *Current protection measures*).

In 2014, SNH provided further evidence and formal advice to the Scottish government on the NCMPA proposals for *Southern Trench*, and three other areas (*North-east Lewis, Sea of Hebrides, and Shiant East Bank*).⁹⁸ At that time, modifications of the boundaries of the recommended MPA included its westward expansion, to include an area of above-average densities of minke whale (*B. acutorostrata*). White-beaked dolphin (*L. albirostris*) was also removed as a feature of the proposal, because it was not possible to identify areas considered as essential within the area.

In 2015, a network-scale assessment was carried out to evaluate the adequacy of the Scottish MPA network with respect to the MPA search features.⁹⁹ That assessment included both designated NCMPAs and the four proposed areas (including *Southern Trench*) for which government approval was still pending. The assessment concluded that the protection of *Southern Trench* was necessary in order to have sufficient representation of the feature 'burrowed mud'. It further stated the designation of *Southern Trench* was required in order to provide sufficient representation of minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*), fronts and shelf deeps in OSPAR Region II (Greater North Sea).⁹⁹

Following an announcement in 2018 that the Scottish government was providing additional resources for the development of the four pending NCMPAs,¹⁰⁰ a public consultation was launched in 2019 on the designation of the sites.¹⁰¹ The official proposal for the *Southern Trench* NCMPA listed four proposed protected biodiversity features (burrowed mud, fronts, minke whale, and shelf deeps) and two geodiversity features (Quaternary of Scotland and submarine mass movement).^{102,103} At least 182 participants, including Oceana, responded to the consultation.¹⁰⁴ At the time of writing, the analysis report from the consultation had not yet been released, and the protection of the area was still pending.

Figure 6. Designated and proposed MPAs in the Aberdeenshire area. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ SNH,⁹² WDCS/HWDT/CRRU.⁹⁵

Lion's mane jellyfish (*Cyanea capillata*).
© OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

© OCEANA/Carlos Minguel

OCEANA SURVEYS

VISUAL SURVEYS (ROV AND SCUBA)

Oceana surveyed the waters off the Aberdeenshire coast as part of an eight-week, at-sea research expedition carried out in the North Sea in 2017. This expedition aimed to gather first-hand information from areas of known or potential ecological importance, but from which data on benthos were lacking. Surveys of these zones were carried out onboard the research survey vessel *MV Neptune*, a fully-equipped vessel of 49.85 m overall length and 10 m extreme breadth.

Research was conducted off the Aberdeenshire coast between 27 June and 3 July 2017, with a total of six days of work at sea in the area (Figure 7). Survey sites were selected based on known or potential features of interest, and also based on consultation with Marine Scotland and SNH prior to the expedition, with particular interest being paid to potential *Sabellaria spinulosa* reef sites.

The seabed was explored mostly by low-impact, visual means, using a remotely operated vehicle (ROV) with a high-definition camera, and via professional SCUBA divers, who produced high-definition video footage and high-resolution still images.

For ROV image recording, a Saab Seaeye Falcon DR ROV was used, equipped with a High Definition Video (HDV) camera of 1920x1080 resolution, 1/2.9" Exmor R CMOS Sensor, minimum scene illumination of 3-11 Lux, and a 4.48 mm, f/1.8 3.4 zoom lens. Images were recorded both in high definition (to film specific features of interest) and low definition (for the total duration of surveys), along with position, depth, course and time. Lasers on the ROV were used in order to estimate sizes and abundances. Considering the average speed and the wide angle of the camera (i.e., it was able to film transects of ca. 1.5 m width), the ROV allowed the observation of around 550-650 m² per hour of seabed.

Across the survey area the ROV was deployed in seven locations, three of which were in the proposed *Southern Trench* MPA (Figure 7). The depth range of the ROV surveys was 42-244 m. Samples of key habitat-forming species were also collected (by means of the robotic arm of the ROV) for detailed analyses to confirm preliminary identifications.

SCUBA surveys were carried out by eight professional divers, divided into two teams; each team comprised a photographer, a videographer, and two safety divers. The divers surveyed five areas: one within *Fowlsheugh* SPA, three within *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA, and one

off the coast of Fraserburgh, ranging in depth from 8-17 m. A total of five samples were taken during two of the dives in the *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* area.

Following the expedition, all of the videos and still images filmed by the ROV and divers were analysed by Oceana scientists, who identified all of the visible species identified to the finest taxonomic level possible.

INFAUNAL SAMPLING

Infaunal community composition was examined using a 12 litre Van Veen grab sampler, and specimens retained on 0.5 mm and 1 mm mesh sieves were kept and identified. In total, 21 grab samples were obtained (one within the *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA, 11 within the proposed *Southern Trench* MPA, and the rest in unprotected waters off the coast of Aberdeenshire). Surveyed sites ranged in depth from 30 m to 223 m. This provided ground-truth data for the footage observed on the ROV, and also biological and sediment samples across the survey area.

OCEANOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS

Water column profiles on various oceanographic parameters were obtained at four locations in the survey area, using a Valeport MIDAS Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth recorder (CTD). This CTD is capable of reaching depths of 7000 m, but in this survey the greatest depth reached with the CTD was 158 m. With the CTD, data were obtained on dissolved oxygen (% saturation), pressure (dbar), temperature (°C), conductivity (ms/cm), fluorescence (ug/L), salinity (psu) and density (kg/m³). Parameters were measured at 1 m depth intervals during both descent and ascent, yielding 851 measurements for each parameter. One of the CTD sample locations lay off the north coast of Fraserburgh, one off the coast of Rattray Head, and the final two off the coast of Peterhead, one of which was within the *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA.

Squat lobster (*Galathea intermedia*).
© OCEANA/ Carlos Minguell

Figure 7. Survey points in the Aberdeenshire survey area during the 2017 Oceana North Sea expedition. Points are shown according to sampling type (i.e., ROV, SCUBA, grab samples, and CTD). Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute.⁹

RESULTS

OCEANOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS

Data on oceanographic parameters in the four sites are shown in Figure 8. The deepest site sampled with a CTD was off the north coast of Fraserburgh, at a depth of 158 m. The water profile here revealed a temperature range of 9.5-11.8 °C, an average salinity of 35 psu and a fluorescence range of 0.1-4.8 ug/L, with the peak fluorescence reading at 26 m. This site had the highest fluorescence concentrations of the four sites sampled. A CTD deployed off the coast of Rattray Head reached a depth of 85 m and recorded temperatures ranging from 10.9-12.6 °C, and average salinity of 33.9 psu and a fluorescence range of 1.7-4.1 ug/l peaking at 47 m depth.

The third CTD deployment was within the SPA *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* and was the shallowest of the CTD sites, reaching depths of 42 m. There, the temperature ranged from 11.7 to 12.0 °C with an average salinity of 34.7 psu. The fluorescence levels recorded there were lower than those recorded off Rattray Head and Fraserburgh, ranging from 0.9-2.4 ug/L. Similarly, the final CTD conducted further offshore of Peterhead revealed fluorescence concentrations ranging from 0.3-2.8 ug/L. The temperature ranged from 9.7-12.0 °C and average salinity was 34.8 psu.

Fluorescence concentration can be used to infer chlorophyll and coloured dissolved organic matter levels. The higher levels of fluorescence found in the northern survey area may have been due to two small mesoscale oceanographic features in the Moray Firth. These features are the Dooley Current, which transports cold north Atlantic water into the northern North Sea and into the Moray Firth¹³ and a plume feature which consists of warmer water flowing from the inner Moray Firth out into the North Sea.³⁵ When the plume is more dominant than the cold-water current, there is an increase in phytoplankton biomass in the southern outer Moray Firth.³⁵ As such, the oceanographic regime in the northern sector of the survey area may have resulted in the higher fluorescence concentration levels compared to the eastern coast of Aberdeenshire.

Figure 8. CTD profiles of the water column at four sites in Aberdeenshire. Parameters included are temperature (°C), fluorescence concentration (ug/L) and salinity (psu). (A) North coast of Fraserburgh, (B) off the coast of Rattray Head, (C) within *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA, (D) offshore from Peterhead.

COMMUNITY TYPES
AND SPECIES

Oceana documented a total of 351 species, 76 genera and 54 higher-level taxa in the Aberdeenshire survey area (see Annex), in association with 14 habitat types (Figure 9). Our findings are presented by community types categorised to the finest degree of classification according to the EUNIS habitat type hierarchy.¹⁰⁵ All of the communities identified fall under the broad EUNIS habitat classification of Sublittoral sediment (A5). Sublittoral sediment habitats extend from the sublittoral zone to the edge of the bathyal zone (200 m) and encompass a range of sediment types, from mud to boulders.¹⁰⁵ Details of the habitat types and sub-types found are provided below.

Figure 9. Distribution of 14 habitat types documented in the Aberdeenshire survey site during the 2017 Oceana expedition, classified according to the EUNIS habitat hierarchy. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ SNH.⁹²

Sublittoral coarse sediment (A5.1)

Sublittoral coarse sediment includes coarse sand, gravel, pebbles, shingle and cobbles.¹⁰⁵ The typical associated species are bivalves, particularly those belonging to the Veneridae family. During the Oceana expedition, this habitat biotype was found offshore from Aberdeen, in an area of coarse sand at 64 m depth. Here, a grab sample revealed a total of 22 species of bivalves, including a specimen of *Arctica islandica* and of some species of Veneridae, such as *Venus cassina*. Other bivalves found include *Timoclea ovata*, *Parvicardium pinnatulum*, *Astarte* spp. and *Nucula* spp. Several echinoderms were included in the grab sample, including *Echinocyamus pusillus* and *Amphiura filiformis*. Tubes of *Sabellaria spinulosa* were also found attached to bivalve shells and cobbles.

Circalittoral coarse sediment (A5.14)

A sub-category of Sublittoral coarse sediment, circalittoral coarse sediment is defined by coarse sands, gravel and shingle in depths over 15-20 m.¹⁰⁵ These habitats are characterised by infaunal polychaetes, mobile crustaceans and bivalves. This habitat type was found in multiple locations including offshore from Aberdeen, within the Southern Trench area, within *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast SPA* and outside *Fowlsheugh SPA*. Offshore from Aberdeen was home to mobile crustaceans, including *Cancer pagurus*, *Galathea* sp., *Munida sarsi* and *Pandalus montagui*, and bivalves such as *Abra prismatica*, *Mimachlamys varia*, *Tellina* spp. and *Timoclea ovata*. Within the Southern Trench area, four grab samples were characteristic of this habitat. All four grabs contained mobile crustaceans such as amphipods, *Eualus cranchii*, and *Strobopagurus gracilipes*, and polychaetes. Tubes of *S. spinulosa* were found attached to shells, and densely covered collected cobbles and pebbles, at some of the grab survey samples collected. Bivalves were also found in these grabs with the most diverse and abundant sample comprising; a total of 23 species and 86 individuals. A grab sample from *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast SPA* contained a diverse array of polychaetes, including *Amphectine auricoma*, *Lagis koreni*, *Owenia fusiformis* and *S. spinulosa* as well as the sponge *Leucosolenia* sp., bivalves and crustaceans. Similarly, a grab sample from outside of *Fowlsheugh SPA* had a comparable composition, with three species of polychaetes identified alongside bivalves and amphipods.

Sublittoral sand (A5.2)

Sublittoral sands are defined as 'clean medium to fine sands or non-cohesive slightly muddy sands on open coasts, offshore or in estuaries and marine inlets'.¹⁰⁵ The typical associated taxa include polychaetes, bivalves and amphipods. This habitat type and the associated community were found offshore from Aberdeen in a grab sample. An array of bivalves was found (12 species), including *Abra alba*, *Chamelea striatula*, *Nuculua nucleus*, *Tellina* spp. and *Venus cassina*. The substrate type was slightly muddy sand at a depth of 41 m.

Circalittoral fine sand (A5.25)

This habitat types consists of fine sands in deeper water (>15-20 m) and is characterised by echinoderms, including pea urchin (*Echinocyamus pusillus*), polychaetes and bivalves. Circalittoral fine sand was found in the furthest sampling site from the shore, off the east coast of Aberdeen. The depth ranged from 70-100 m with fine sand and muddy sand. Among the sampled fauna, *E. pusillus* was abundant, with a total of 56 individuals recorded from the grab samples. Other echinoderms documented included *Amphiura filiformis* and *Echinocardium flavescens*. A diverse range of bivalves were found, including *Abra prismatica*, *Arctica islandica*, *Astarte montagui*, the habitat-forming species *Modiolus modiolus*, *Tellina pygmaea* and *Timoclea ovata*. Polychaetes found included *Hyalinoecia tubicola* and *Sabellaria spinulosa*, of which two small aggregations of tubes were collected in one grab.

Sublittoral mud (A5.3): Seapens and burrowing megafauna in circalittoral fine mud (A5.361)

This habitat type is characterised by mud at depths greater than 15 m, supporting populations of *P. phosphorea* and *V. mirabilis*. The mud may contain burrows due to the presence of burrowing megafauna such as Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*). This habitat type was recorded by the ROV within the Southern Trench at depths ranging from 163-244 m. During this survey, 104 individuals of *Pennatula phosphorea* were found in burrowed mud sites. *Cerianthus lloydii* was also recorded, as well as *Liocarcinus depurator* and *Pagurus bernhardus*, and brittlestars (*Ophiura albida* and *Ophiothrix fragilis*). Burrowed mud was observed in this site, although *N. norvegicus* was not encountered.

Figure 10. *Astrorhiza limicola* and *Pennatula phosphorea*.

Sublittoral mud (A5.3): Deep circalittoral mud (A5.37)

Typically below 50-70 m, this habitat type is characterised by muddy sediment and dominated by polychaetes and high numbers of bivalves, echinoderms and foraminifera. This habitat type was found in a grab sample taken in the Southern Trench at a depth of 200 m. Within this sample there were echinoderms *Amphiura chiajei* and *Echinocyamus pusillus*, bivalves Semelidae and *Nucula* sp., and also polychaetes.

Sublittoral mixed sediments (A5.4)

This habitat type consists of heterogeneous sediments (including muddy gravelly sand and cobbles and pebbles) that can support a wide range of infauna and epibiota including polychaetes, bivalves, echinoderms, sponges, anemones, hydroids and bryozoans. It was documented in *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA during an ROV survey, and hosted seven species of cnidaria including hydroids (*Kirchenpaueria pinnata*, *Nemertesia antennina*, and *Tubularia indivisa*) and anemones (*Urticina eques* and *Cerianthus lloydii*). Over 400 individuals of *Asterias rubens* were documented along this transect. Bryozoans present included *Flustra foliacea*, *Membranipora membranacea* and *Parasmittina trispinosa*, while sponges documented included *Grantia compressa*, the habitat-forming species *Stelligera stuposa* and *Sycon ciliatum*. Macroalgae such as *Delesseria sanguina*, *Heterosiphonia plumosa* and *Desmarestia aculeata* were also documented in low numbers.

Five grab samples taken within the Southern Trench area also fell under this habitat type. These samples contained anthozoans such as *Caryophyllia smithii* and *Stomphia coccinea*, hydrozoans such as *Lafoea dumosa* and *Tubularia indivisa*, and various echinoderms and bryozoans. Other grab samples representing this habitat type were taken offshore from the east coast of Aberdeen, and included habitat-forming species, such as *Tellina* spp. and remains of *Arctica islandica*. Tubes of *Sabellaria spinulosa* were found densely covering some shells and rocks collected in one grab sample in that area.

Circalittoral mixed sediments (A5.44)

This biotype is also characterised by mixed sediments that host a variety of communities, particularly hydroids (*Nemertesia* spp. and *Hydrallmania falcata*). Circalittoral mixed sediment areas were recorded in the majority of ROV surveys both within the Southern Trench area and also in waters offshore from Aberdeen. The ROV survey within the Southern Trench recorded more than 120 individuals of sickle hydroid (*H. falcata*) and more than 490 individuals of *Nemertesia* spp. Offshore from Aberdeen, three ROV surveys documented more than 181 individuals of *H. falcata* and over 233 of *Nemertesia* spp. Some sponges were also present, including the habitat-forming species *Polymastia boletiformis*, *Halicolona urceolus*, and *Suberites* sp.

Figure 11. *Nemertesia antennina*.

Cerianthus lloydii and other burrowing anemones in circalittoral muddy mixed sediment (A5.441)

This habitat type is characterised by sandy muddy gravel that hosts burrowing anemones such as North Sea tube anemone (*Cerianthus lloydii*). An ROV survey site in the Southern Trench comprised this biotype due to the muddy sandy sediment present and the presence of *C. lloydii* and *Cerianthus membranaceus*. Hermit crab (*Pagurus bernhardus*) was also present, along with common sea star (*Asterias rubens*). Other species within this community included scallop (*Pecten maximus*), sand mason worm (*Lanice conchilega*) and sponges such as *Antho (Antho) dichotoma*, *Haliclona urceolus* and *Suberites* spp.

Figure 12. *Cerianthus lloydii*.

Ophiothrix fragilis and/or *Ophiocomina nigra* brittlestar beds on sublittoral mixed sediment (A5.445)

The sediment in this habitat biotype is dominated by brittle stars *Ophiothrix fragilis* and *Ophiocomina nigra*, which form dense beds. An example of this community was observed in the north of Fraserburgh in the Southern Trench area, where more than 1081 individuals of *O. nigra* and more than 1281 individuals of *O. fragilis* were found on rocky sandy sediments. The soft coral dead man's fingers (*Alcyonium digitatum*) was frequently encountered, as well as hydroids (*Nemertesia* spp.) and anemones (*Urticina* spp). Various species of crustacean were also documented, including *Cancer pagurus*, *Galathea* sp., *Inachus dorsettensis*, *Munida* spp. and *Necora puber*. Some sponges were also observed, including *Antho* sp., *Halichondria* (*Halichondria*) *panicea* and *Hymedesmia* sp. These communities inhabited areas of rocks and sand in depths of around 45 m.

Figure 13. Brittlestars covering the seafloor.

Deep circalittoral mixed sediments (A5.45)

This habitat type comprises substrates of slightly muddy mixed gravelly sand and stones or shell. Associated species typically include a diversity of polychaetes and bivalves, and some areas may support horse mussel (*Modiolus modiolus*). Grab samples in two locations revealed the presence of the habitat type: one in the Southern Trench, and one offshore from Aberdeen. The samples indicated that polychaetes were present in both sites, while six species of bivalves were recorded in the Southern Trench (including the habitat-forming species *Tellina pygmaea*) and 12 species of bivalves in the offshore Aberdeen grab (including remains of *Arctica islandica*).

Sublittoral macrophyte-dominated sediment (A5.5)

This habitat type includes maërl beds, macroalgae on mixed sediment, seagrass beds and lagoonal angiosperm communities. All of the SCUBA dive surveys documented this habitat biotype, and showcased high diversity and abundance of macroalgae, particularly of tangle (*Laminaria hyperborea*), the red alga *Phycodrys rubens*, and encrusting red alga *Phymatolithon lenormandii*. The first dive was conducted within Fowlsheugh SPA, and documented more than 78 individuals of *L. hyperborea* and over 61 specimens of *P. rubens*. A dive conducted on the north coast of Aberdeenshire recorded nine species of macroalgae, including more than 573 individuals of *L. hyperborea*. This kelp forest supported populations of echinoderms such as *Echinus esculentus*, *Henricia* sp. and *Marthasterias glacialis*, as well as seven species of crustaceans, and more than 361 individuals of dead man's fingers (*Alcyonium digitatum*). Three dives were conducted within the Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast SPA, where more than 668 individuals of *L. hyperborea* were documented, alongside other macroalgae species including *Alaria esculenta*, *Desmarestia* spp. and *Saccharina latissima*. These sites hosted over 16 species of crustaceans, nine species of tunicates, and nine species of bryozoans. Grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) were documented during four of these SCUBA surveys, both from the surface and inside submerged caves (with one individual found in one cave, and a group of nine individuals in a second cave).

Figure 14. *Laminaria hyperborea* forest. © OCEANA/ Carlos Minguell

Saccharina latissima and red seaweeds on infralittoral sediments (A5.521)

This biotype comprises infralittoral mixed muddy substrata communities characterised by sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*), with mixed filamentous and foliose red macroalgae. This habitat type was found during a SCUBA dive inside the Buchan Ness

to Collieston Coast SPA. During this dive, over 60 individuals of *S. latissima* were documented alongside an abundance of red macroalgae. Other brown macroalgae documented in this habitat included *Alaria esculenta*, *Fucus serratus* and *Laminaria hyperborea*.

Figure 15. *Saccharina latissima*.
© OCEANA/ Carlos Minguell

Sublittoral biogenic reefs (A5.6): *Sabellaria spinulosa* on stable circalittoral mixed sediment (A5.611)

This habitat includes the reef-forming polychaete known as ross worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*) in high abundances on mixed sediment. Such concentrations of *S. spinulosa* were documented in three ROV surveys conducted off the coast of Aberdeen, which revealed a total of 36 aggregations of *S. spinulosa* amongst rocks and sand. The size of these aggregations ranged in size from 10 cm to more than 80 cm width. The ross worm aggregations provided a hard substrate for species to colonise in otherwise sandy habitat. Species found living on and amongst the *S. spinulosa* included hydroids such as *Tubularia indivisa*, *Nemertesia* spp., and *Hydrallmania falcata*; dead man's fingers (*Alcyonium digitatum*); and anemone *Urticina* sp.

Consolidation of sediment by *S. spinulosa* tubes was also documented in six grab samples from depths of 30 m to 250 m in sand, coarse sediment, and mixed sediment sites (see corresponding habitat type sections, above) in the same offshore Aberdeen area where reefs were observed via ROV, and in other locations. Although the extent of coverage or size of aggregations cannot be determined from grab samples, they nevertheless confirmed the presence of *S. spinulosa* aggregations in locations that had not previously been documented (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Overview of known ross worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*) aggregations and reefs in the Aberdeenshire area. Points are located where reefs have been documented. Research organisations and survey years are detailed in the legend. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ Oceana (present study), SNH/JNCC/MSS,¹⁸ SNH/Cefas,¹⁷ SNH/MSS,²¹ MMT,²² and SNH.²²

Figure 17. *Sabellaria spinulosa* reef with laser points (10 cm apart) for size reference.

The Oceana expedition documented 16 species and seven habitat types in the waters of Aberdeenshire that are considered priorities for conservation because these features are included within international or Scottish frameworks that recognise their threatened status and/or establish requirements for their legal protection (Table 4). These include: the OSPAR List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats;¹⁰⁶ the EU Habitats Directive;¹⁰⁷ the list of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) habitats and indicator taxa from the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES);¹⁰⁸ the Scottish Biodiversity List;¹⁰⁹ and the list of Priority Marine Features (PMFs), which are recognised priorities for marine conservation in Scottish waters.²⁴ Of the 14 PMFs recorded, six are further considered to be MPA search features,^{97,110} which are used to guide the development of the Scottish MPA network. The occurrence of features listed in Table 4 deserves special consideration with respect to the biodiversity value of the area and required management measures. These features are discussed in more detail below.

Most of the 16 species of conservation interest found in the survey area (Figure 18) were fishes, including sandeels (*Ammodytes* spp.) and gadids such as cod (e.g., *Gadus morhua*) and whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*). Also documented were six species that are listed by ICES as indicators of North Atlantic deep-water VMEs: ecosystems that are especially vulnerable to impacts from fishing activities. These species included cnidarians (*Caryophyllia smithii*, *Cerianthus lloydii*, *C. membranaceus*, *Pachycerianthus multiplicatus*, and *Pennatula phosporea*) and one species of sponge (*Polymastia boletiformis*); they are considered representative of four specific VME habitat types.¹⁰⁸

Surveys also recorded the remains of seven specimens of ocean quahog (*Arctica islandica*), in four grab samples taken at depths between 64 m and 127 m. This mollusc is very vulnerable due to its long lifespan (which can exceed 500 years),¹¹¹ size (which can reach 100 mm in length),¹¹² and preferences for soft sandy bottoms, where it suffers from many anthropogenic impacts. The protection of the species is a priority under OSPAR for the Greater North Sea, where it is under threat and/or decline. In Scotland, ocean quahog is a PMF and an MPA search feature, and there remains a noted lack of data on its abundance in the areas where it is known to occur.⁹⁹

Reefs and other aggregations formed by ross worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*) were one of the features of greatest conservation interest that was observed during Oceana's surveys in Aberdeenshire waters (Figure 19). The importance of reefs formed by these tube-building polychaetes has been well recognised, as they increase the habitat complexity of soft bottoms and have been defined as biodiversity hotspots due to their associated species richness.^{113,114} The conservation value of *S. spinulosa* reef habitats is highest where they occur in areas of sediment or mixed sediment bottoms, such as off Aberdeenshire; they provide a biogenic habitat that rises above the seabed, thereby permitting the settlement of epibenthic and infaunal species not found in adjacent habitats.^{6,115}

Given their ecological importance, the protection of ross worm reefs is included under two major international conservation frameworks that are relevant for North Sea waters. The EU Habitats Directive covers biogenic concretions under the 'Reefs' habitat type of community interest, and specifically mentions *S. spinulosa* as a reef-forming species in the North Sea.¹¹⁶ OSPAR also includes *S. spinulosa* reefs on its List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats, and establishes recommended measures for their protection, such as limiting certain fisheries and aggregate extraction practices.¹¹⁷

In the waters of Aberdeenshire, several surveys during the past decade had documented the presence of *S. spinulosa* aggregations (Figure 16), including locations with extensive reefs that hosted high levels of biodiversity.²² In 2017, both Oceana's research and SNH surveys¹⁸ revealed the occurrence of ross worm aggregations and reefs in additional sites off the coast of

Grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*).
© OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

Aberdeen, Peterhead, and in the Southern Trench (at a depth of 250 m) (Figure 16). This suggests that *S. spinulosa* may be much more widespread in this area, and that there is the potential for additional reefs to be discovered.

A second key habitat type of importance documented Oceana's surveys in Aberdeenshire waters is burrowed mud, a recognised conservation priority both internationally and within Scotland. 'Sea pen and burrowing megafauna communities' are included on the OSPAR List of Threatened and/or Declining Habitats,¹⁰⁶ on the basis of both documented declines and sensitivity to threats. Sea pen fields are also considered a VME habitat type,¹⁰⁸ which is threatened by activities that cause physical disturbance to the seabed, primarily demersal fisheries (in particular, trawl fisheries) that directly damage fragile invertebrate such as sea pens, cause changes in benthic community structure and function, and resuspend fine particles of sediment.¹¹⁸ Within Scotland, the habitat type 'Mud habitats in deep water' is considered a conservation priority;¹⁰⁹ burrowed mud is both a PMF and an MPA search feature^{24,97} and is one of the four biodiversity features that would be protected if the *Southern Trench* proposed NCMPA were designated.¹⁰² Moreover, a network-level assessment carried out in 2015 by JNCC, SNH, and Marine Scotland concluded that without the protection of the *Southern Trench*, this habitat type would not be adequately protected in Scottish waters.⁹⁹

Also worthy of note were rich habitats comprised by macroalgae. Large laminarians or kelps can create large and dense forests, together with foliose Rhodophyta (red algae). These species can provide an extensive 'canopy' under which many other species live, and a surface to which other organisms may attach. These habitats are of recognised importance at both the European and national level. The Habitats Directive descriptions of various types of reefs include red, brown and green macroalgae among the characteristic species of reef vegetation,¹¹⁶ and different types of kelp and macroalgal communities are considered both PMFs and MPA search features in Scotland.^{24,97} Furthermore, kelp forests in the North Sea are currently in the process of being listed as a threatened and/or declining habitat by OSPAR. During Oceana's surveys, kelp forests were documented on the northern and eastern coasts of Aberdeenshire, including areas inside the *Fowlsheugh* and *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPAs. Key species that comprised these habitats were tangle (*Laminaria hyperborea*) and sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*), mixed with a variety of red macroalgae and other brown macroalgal species. Associated fauna included other habitat-forming species such as the soft coral *Alcyonium digitatum*, as well as ascidians, bryozoans, hydrozoans, sponges, anemones, echinoderms, and molluscs.

Submerged caves represented another important habitat type found during Oceana's surveys. Caves are listed under Annex I of the EU Habitats Directive¹⁰⁷ and based on the conclusions

of the last biogeographical seminar to assess the status of the marine Natura 2000 Network, the UK has not yet sufficiently protected this habitat type in Scotland. During this seminar, it was highlighted that such caves provide important habitat for grey seal (*Halichoerus grypus*), and the UK government representative noted the difficulty of identifying cave areas. During Oceana's surveys, four submerged caves were documented inside *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA, and grey seals and a school of sandeels were found inside them.

In addition to these habitat types, aggregations of burrowing anemones (*Cerianthus* spp.) and phosphorescent sea pen (*Pennatula phosphorea*) were also recorded, which are considered VME habitat types by ICES (see *Threatened and Protected Species*).¹⁰⁸

Table 4. Benthic features of conservation interests documented in Aberdeenshire during the 2017 Oceana expedition, and the international and national frameworks under which they are recognised as threatened, protected, and/or priorities for conservation. HD: EU Habitats Directive; VME: Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (both habitats and indicator species); PMF: Priority Marine Feature.

Features	International Frameworks			National Frameworks		
	OSPAR ¹⁰⁶	HD ¹⁰⁷	VME ¹⁰⁸	Scottish Biodiversity List ¹⁰⁹	PMF ²⁴	MPA search feature ¹¹⁰
<i>Ammodytes marinus</i>				X	X	
<i>Ammodytes tobianus</i>				X	X	X
<i>Arctica islandica</i>	X				X	X
<i>Caryophyllia smithii</i>			X			
<i>Cerianthus lloydii</i>			X			
<i>Cerianthus membranaceus</i>			X			
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	X			X	X	
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>				X	X	
<i>Molva molva</i>				X	X	
<i>Pachycerianthus multiplicatus</i>			X	X	X ^a	
<i>Pennatula phosphorea</i>			X			
<i>Pollachius virens</i>					X	
<i>Polymastia boletiformis</i>			X			
<i>Polyplumaria flabellata</i>				X		
<i>Simnia patula</i>				X		
<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>				X	X	

Habitats	Burrowed mud			X	X	X
	Burrowing anemone aggregations			X	X	
	Kelp and macroalgal communities		Annex I: 1170 Reefs		X	X
	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i> reefs	X	Annex I: 1170 Reefs			
	Sea pens and burrowing megafauna communities	X		X	X	X
	Submerged caves		Annex I: 8330 Submerged or partially submerged sea caves			
	Subtidal sands and gravels			X	X	X

a. *P. multiplicatus* is a component species under the PMF 'Burrowed mud'.

Beyond the documented PMFs that comprise habitat types, Oceana also found species that are considered indicators of three additional PMFs, both inside and outside the proposed *Southern Trench* NCMFA. Further research would therefore be needed to confirm whether the following three PMFs are also present in the area:

- 'Northern sea fan and sponge communities - Deep sponge communities (circalittoral)'. The indicator species *Stelligera stuposa* (an erect branching sponge) was found outside the proposed MPA, together with other sponge species (e.g., *Sycon ciliatum* and *Grantia compressa*). Inside the *Southern Trench* area, a variety of sponge species growing on boulders were recorded, including *Antho* spp., *Haliclona urceolus*, *Suberites carnosus*, and *Suberites* spp. on deep bottom, and erect sponge species (i.e., *Antho* sp., *Halichondria panicea* and *Hymedesmia* sp.) in a shallower area. In both locations, other typical associated species for this biotope complex were also recorded.
- 'Horse mussel beds - *Modiolus modiolus* beds with *Chlamys varia*, sponges, hydroids and bryozoans on slightly tide-swept very sheltered circalittoral mixed substrata'. Shells of both *M. modiolus* and *Mimachlamys varia* (the accepted name for *Chlamys varia*) were collected together in a grab sample at 70 m depth, outside the proposed NCMFA.

Figure 18. Species of conservation interest documented in Aberdeenshire during the 2017 Oceana expedition. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ SNH.⁹²

- 'Inshore deep mud with burrowing heart urchins - *Brissopsis lyrifera* and *Amphiura chiajei* in circalittoral mud'. Individuals of heart urchin (*B. lyrifera*) were collected in a grab sample from a location close to a second sampling site where individuals of brittlestar (*A. chiajei*) were also collected in two grab surveys. Both points were located inside the proposed NCMPA.

Blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) and barnacles. © OCEANA/ Carlos Minguell

Figure 19. Habitats of conservation interest documented in Aberdeenshire during the 2017 Oceana expedition. Sources: EMODnet,⁷ EEA,⁸ Flanders Marine Institute,⁹ SNH.⁹²

SPECIES OF COMMERCIAL INTEREST AND ESSENTIAL FISH HABITAT

A total of 26 species of fishes were identified in the survey area (see Annex), many of which are commercially exploited (see Table 2). Of these species, the highest documented abundance of adult fishes was for dab (*Limanda limanda*), followed by sandeels (*Ammodytes* spp.). Records of juvenile fishes were dominated by gadids, such as whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), cod (*Gadus morhua*), and poor cod (*Trisopterus minutus*).

The commercial species documented by Oceana included various fishes for which the waters of Aberdeenshire represent essential fish habitat (EFH): habitats that play a critical role during species' life cycles, such as spawning, nursery, or feeding grounds.³⁹ Specifically, spawning grounds have been

documented for at least eight species (of which Oceana recorded five), while nursery grounds have been identified in the area for at least 20 species (of which Oceana recorded eight) (Table 5).

For instance, Aberdeenshire waters encompass spawning and nursery grounds for sandeels (*Ammodytidae*).^{37,38,119} During the Oceana surveys, sandeels were observed off both the north and east coasts of Aberdeenshire, including within the *Buchan Ness to Collieston* SPA. Shoals of *Ammodytes* spp. were recorded during surveys close to the east coast, near Fraserburgh and Peterhead. The local prevalence of sandeels in the area was unsurprising, given that the area is closed to sandeel fishing⁸⁹ on the basis of its known importance for these fishes.

The area also provides EFH for an array of gadids, including six species that were observed by Oceana (Table 5). For example, juveniles of cod (*G. morhua*), haddock (*M. aeglefinus*), and whiting (*M. merlangus*) were found in areas of mixed sediment and in shallow areas dominated by macroalgae on the east coast of Aberdeenshire. For all three species, safeguarding EFH is especially important, given the current status of the stocks. Although cod appeared to have been recovering from steep biomass declines during the 1970s until the mid-2000s, the most recent assessment of the population in the North Sea, eastern English Channel, and the Skagerrak indicates that cod in these areas has once again been declining.¹²⁰ It is currently considered to be below safe limits and remains subject to ongoing overfishing. One of the critical aspects highlighted in the assessment is the fact that recruitment has been poor since 1998 – which points even more strongly to the need to protect cod spawning and nursery grounds, to facilitate stock recovery.

Shorthorn sculpin (*Myoxocephalus scorpius*). © OCEANA/ Juan Cuetos

While the status of haddock (*M. aeglefinus*) in the area is considered to be better than that of cod, the most recent stock assessment for haddock in the North Sea, West of Scotland, and the Skagerrak also raises concerns about stock recruitment. It notes that recruitment has been low since the year 2000, with only occasional larger year classes, which have been decreasing in size over time.¹²¹ The stock remains subject to unsustainable levels of fishing pressure.

Similarly, the 2019 assessment for whiting (*M. merlangus*) indicated that the stock in the North Sea and eastern English Channel is below safe biological limits, and that fishing pressure has been above sustainable levels for the past forty years (with the exception of the year 2005).¹²² Recruitment in the last two years has been below average, again suggesting that measures to protect juvenile fishes may be especially important.

It should be noted that in addition to fishes, the waters of Aberdeenshire represent important spawning and nursery grounds for Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*),¹²³ although no individuals were observed during Oceana’s surveys.

Table 5. Fish species with known essential fish habitat (EFH), specifically spawning and nursery grounds, in Aberdeenshire waters,^{37,38,123,124} along with the abundances of fish species recorded during the Oceana 2017 expedition. Species for which no abundance is indicated were not observed during the expedition.

Species	Known EFH		Oceana observations	
	Spawning area	Nursery ground	Juveniles	Adults
<i>Agonus cataphractus</i>			-	23
Ammodytidae	X	X	-	>143
<i>Aphia minuta</i>			-	>21
<i>Arnoglossus laterna</i>			-	2
<i>Callionymus maculatus</i>			-	8
<i>Callionymus</i> sp.			-	1
<i>Chelidonichthys cuculus</i>			-	4
<i>Chirolophis ascanii</i>			-	1
<i>Clupea harengus</i>	X	X	-	-
Cottidae			-	1
<i>Dipturus batis</i>		X	-	-
Gadidae			>32	-

<i>Gadus morhua</i>	X	X	8	-
<i>Galeorhinus galeus</i>		X	-	-
<i>Hyperoplus lanceolatus</i>			-	2
<i>Labrus mixtus</i>			-	3
<i>Limanda limanda</i>			-	>299
<i>Liparis liparis</i>			-	2
<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>		X	-	-
<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i>		X	3	4
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	X	X	26	1
<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>		X	-	-
<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>		X	-	-
<i>Microstomus kitt</i>	X	X	1	2
<i>Molva molva</i>		X	2	4
<i>Myoxocephalus scorpius</i>			-	5
<i>Myxine glutinosa</i>			-	4
<i>Pholis gunnellus</i>			-	8
<i>Phrynorhombus norvegicus</i>			-	1
Pleuronectiformes			-	1
<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i>	X	X	-	-
<i>Pollachius virens</i>		X	2	-
<i>Raja clavata</i>		X	-	-
<i>Raja montagui</i>		X	-	-
<i>Scomber scombrus</i>		X	-	-
<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	X	X	-	-
<i>Squalus acanthias</i>		X	-	-
<i>Taurulus bubalis</i>			-	7
<i>Triglops murrayi</i>			-	3
<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>	X	X	4	7
<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>			8	4

Considering the high level of demersal fishing activity in the area present in the area (see *Threats*), it was expected that surveys would find evidence of trawling activity and creel fisheries in the survey area. While no trawl marks were observed, some evidence of fishing activity was observed, as three pots were found in the survey area during SCUBA dives within *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast SPA*. Two of these traps were in use, while one had been discarded.

The area's close proximity to the coast and busy shipping routes led to the expectation that there may have been considerable amounts of marine debris in the survey site. Nevertheless, only two pieces of litter were observed during two ROV surveys: glass at 45 m depth in the Southern Trench and a plastic pipe at 44 m depth within *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast SPA*. However, microplastics (which cannot be observed in ROV and SCUBA footage) were collected in ten out of 21 grab samples. Microplastic obtained in these grabs were found at depths ranging from 30 m to 250 m. Five of these grabs were concentrated within the Southern Trench, and the rest were located along and offshore of the eastern coast of Aberdeenshire.

Figure 20. Fishing trap.
© OCEANA/ Carlos Minguell

© OCEANA/ Juan Cuertos

PROPOSAL FOR PROTECTION

The sea surrounding Aberdeenshire is characterised by a rich diversity of benthic ecosystems, ranging from kelp forests along the coast to burrowed mud within the deep waters of the Southern Trench. These ecosystems encompass an array of features that are recognised priorities for conservation, at both the Scottish and international level. These features include species such as sandeels (*Ammodytes* spp.) and fireworks anemone (*Pachycerianthus multiplicatus*), and habitats such as ross worm (*Sabellaria spinulosa*) reefs and sea pen and burrowing megafauna communities.

Despite the high biodiversity value of benthic ecosystems in the Oceana survey area, protection of the benthos has been limited to date. Currently, the only measures of benthic protection in place within the area are restrictions on specific fisheries (i.e., Norway pout and sandeels); the only three MPAs that lie within the survey area are designated for the protection of birds (see *Current management measures*) and therefore do not grant any legal protection to the seabed. However, this situation may soon change. The Scottish government has formally recognised the value of benthic biodiversity in nearshore Aberdeenshire waters with its proposal to designate a large area (2536 km²) of the Southern Trench as an NCMPA, to protect burrowed mud habitats and shelf deeps (as well as fronts, minke whale, and geodiversity features).¹⁰² The *Southern Trench* site has been proposed as one of four new NCMPAs that would help to complete the Scottish network of MPAs. At the time of writing, a decision had not yet been announced on its designation.

The Oceana expedition in 2017 added further to knowledge about the rich diversity of benthic life in Aberdeenshire waters. During the expedition, 14 habitat types were recorded in the area, including sea pens and burrowing megafauna, brittle star beds, macroalgal communities and ross worm reefs. These habitat types were associated with high levels of biodiversity, with a total of 351 species, 76 genera and 54 higher-level taxa identified. Among the features documented were 23 features of conservation interest, including species and habitats that are priorities for protection in Scotland and/or internationally.

The Southern Trench clearly represents a biodiversity hotspot, and Oceana strongly supports the designation of the *Southern Trench* NCMPA to protect the rich biological communities found there. The protection of *Southern Trench* would represent a significant step to improve the conservation of the area itself, and to strengthen the network of Scottish MPAs in general. The Marine (Scotland) Act 2010 requires that Scottish Ministers designate NCMPAs as a contribution to a UK-wide network, and that the features protected by Scottish MPAs be representative of UK waters.⁹⁴ In this respect, the protection of burrowed

mud areas in *Southern Trench* is particularly important; Marine Scotland concluded in its 2015 assessment of the sufficiency of the Scottish MPA network that the protection of this feature would be insufficient in Scottish waters if the *Southern Trench* were not designated.⁹⁹

Beyond the four biodiversity features that are proposed for protection in *Southern Trench*, Oceana's surveys indicated the presence of other features of conservation importance within the boundaries of the proposed site and therefore merit further consideration for protection. These features included additional PMFs: kelp forest (composed of *Laminaria hyperborea* and other macroalgae), sandeels (*Ammodytes* spp.), cod (*Gadus morhua*), ling (*Molva molva*), and whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*). Observations also indicated the potential occurrence of three other PMFs (see *Features of conservation interest*), for which further investigation would be needed to confirm their presence and determine their extent.

In addition to PMFs, Oceana's research highlighted the occurrence of another major feature of importance within the *Southern Trench* area that should be prioritised for protection: aggregations of ross worm (*S. spinulosa*). Oceana's findings supported observations from previous surveys that had also found dense encrustations of *S. spinulosa* within the proposed NCMPA (Figure 16). In fact, on the basis of earlier surveys, SNH noted that "*Sabellaria*-dominated habitats probably cover an extensive area in the eastern region of the proposed MPA."¹⁷

Given the decline of *S. spinulosa* reefs in European waters, their listing by OSPAR as a threatened and/or declining habitat in the Greater North Sea, and the fact that these reefs are currently not protected in waters off the east coast of Scotland, further investigation of *S. spinulosa* within the proposed *Southern Trench* site should be prioritised. Depending on the nature and extent of the aggregations, the Scottish government should consider granting them formal protection within the MPA, as well as considering more broadly whether such aggregations should also be added to the list of Scottish PMFs.

Furthermore, Oceana's research showed that the distribution of *S. spinulosa* aggregations outside the *Southern Trench* area is more extensive than was previously known. In particular, Oceana discovered ross worm reefs and aggregations off the east coast of Aberdeenshire, spread across the area immediately to the south of the proposed NCMPA (Figure 16). Based on the extent and distribution of *S. spinulosa* documented, Oceana urges the Scottish authorities to extend the southern boundary of the proposed *Southern Trench* area further to the south, to encompass these vulnerable habitats.

Oceana's findings of *S. spinulosa* aggregations in Aberdeenshire waters add to a growing body of records from both government and industry surveys that emphasise the potential importance of the area for the development of ross worm reefs (see *Known*

ecological features of interest), and therefore the need to identify appropriate measures of protection. One encouraging development in this respect is a project currently being carried out by Marine Scotland, which aims to categorise *S. spinulosa* reefs in the Moray Firth area, assess the applicability of current criteria for protection to those reefs, and to consider options for their conservation. Alongside those efforts, Oceana encourages the Scottish government to conduct comprehensive benthic habitat mapping in the Aberdeenshire area, to identify the presence of any additional *S. spinulosa* reefs and to assess their condition and extent. Many of the known *S. spinulosa* aggregations off Aberdeenshire have been discovered during exploratory ROV surveys in specific areas, rather than broader efforts to map benthic communities and habitats more systematically. It is therefore likely that additional ross worm reefs and aggregations exist in the area. Conducting such research falls within the obligations of the UK as a Contracting Party to the OSPAR Convention, under which seabed habitat surveys and monitoring are among the programmes and measures identified as priority actions for the conservation of *S. spinulosa* reefs.¹²⁵

In addition to *S. spinulosa* aggregations, Oceana documented the presence of other priority features for conservation that lie outside the southern boundary of the proposed *Southern Trench* NCMPA. These features included nine biodiversity PMFs: two habitats and seven species. Specifically, Oceana found kelp beds comprising dense forests of tangle (*L. hyperborea*) and of sugar kelp (*S. latissima*), tide-swept algal communities formed by dense aggregations of toothed wrack (*Fucus serratus*), one low-mobility species (*A. islandica*), and six mobile species (*Ammodytes tobianus*, *G. morhua*, *Halichoerus grypus*, *M. merlangus*, *M. molva*, and *Pollachius virens*). Further research would be needed to confirm whether two additional PMFs occur in the same area (see *Features of conservation interest*). Finally, Oceana's observations of submerged caves within *Buchan Ness to Collieston Coast* SPA further highlight the rich variety of ecosystems that are currently unprotected in the area to the south of *Southern Trench*. Overall, these findings indicate that the *Southern Trench* area does not sufficiently encompass the habitats and species of conservation importance in the vicinity, and that either the boundaries of the proposed site should be extended, or that complementary measures of spatial protection should be developed.

Critically, it is essential that the protection of the *Southern Trench* and other areas of benthic biodiversity in Aberdeenshire waters be effective. According to the proposal for the designation of *Southern Trench* as a NCMPA, the conservation objective of the site is to "conserve" protected features.¹⁰² This choice of objective assumes that the biodiversity features proposed for protection are all considered to be in favourable condition at present. However, it is unclear what the basis is for this assessment. For example, burrowed mud is listed as threatened and/or declining under OSPAR (i.e., 'seapen and burrowing

megafauna communities') in the Greater North Sea, as a result of declines in habitat quality due to demersal fisheries.¹¹⁸ More broadly, the last EU-level assessment of MPAs showed that the conservation status of 71% of protected seabed habitats in the North-East Atlantic region was unfavourable, while the status of the remainder was unknown. Given the intensity of human activities in the region, a more ambitious and appropriate objective for *Southern Trench* would include the recovery of burrowed mud communities, with management measures in line with that aim. In particular, measures to limit the impact of demersal fisheries in Aberdeenshire waters would benefit not only burrowed mud communities, but also other fragile benthic features, such as *S. spinulosa* reefs and aggregations.

Such ambitious efforts are required if Scotland is to achieve the second part of its stated conservation objective for the proposed *Southern Trench* NCMPA: to “make a long-lasting contribution to the MPA network.”¹⁰² With over 60% of the UK's seas under its jurisdiction, Scotland is a key contributor to the development of ecologically coherent networks of MPAs – within Scotland, the UK, and the broader North Sea. Safeguarding the biodiversity richness of Aberdeenshire's waters is an integral part of that process.

Juvenile of Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*).
© OCEANA/ Carlos Minguell

© OCEANA/ Juan Cuertos

REFERENCES

- 1 Brooks, A.J., Kenyon, N.H., Leslie, A., Long, D. & Gordon, J.E. 2013. Characterising Scotland's marine environment to define search locations for new Marine Protected Areas. Part 2: The identification of key geodiversity areas in Scottish waters. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 432.
- 2 Greathead, C.F., Donnan, D.W., Mair, J.M. & Saunders, G.R. 2007. The sea pens *Virgularia mirabilis*, *Pennatula phosphorea* and *Funiculina quadrangularis*: distribution and conservation issues in Scottish waters. *Journal of Marine Biology Association of the United Kingdom*, 87: 1095-1103.
- 3 Jones, J.B. 1992. Environmental impact of trawling on the seabed: a review. *New Zealand Journal of Marine and Freshwater Research*, 26(1): 59-67.
- 4 Tuck, I.D., Hall, S.J., Robertson, M.R., Armstrong, E. & Basford, D.J. 1998. Effects of physical trawling disturbance in a previously unfished sheltered Scottish sea loch. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 162: 227-242.
- 5 Ball, B., Munday, B. & Tuck, I. 2000. Effects of otter trawling on the benthos and environment in muddy sediments. In: *Effects of Fishing on Non-target Species and Habitats: Biological Conservation and Socio-economic Issues*, pp. 69-82. Kaiser, M.J., & de Groot, S.J. (eds.). Blackwell Science, Oxford.
- 6 European Environment Agency. 2012. *Sabellaria spinulosa* on stable circalittoral mixed sediment. EUNIS Habitat Classification 2012. Available from: <http://eunis.eea.europa.eu/habitats/1693>
- 7 EMODnet. 2019. Seabed Habitats. Available from: <https://www.EMODnet-seabedhabitats.eu/access-data/launch-map-viewer/>
- 8 European Environment Agency. 2019. Datasets. Available from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/>
- 9 Flanders Marine Institute. 2019. Maritime Boundaries Geodatabase, version 11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.14284/382>.
- 10 Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). 2004. Strategic Environmental Assessment 5: Environmental Report. UK Government. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/strategic-environmental-assessment-5-environmental-report>
- 11 Holmes, R., Bulat, J., Henni, P., Holt, J., James, C., Kenyon, N., Leslie, A., Long, D., Musson, R., Pearson, S. & Stewart, H. 2004. DTI Strategic Environmental Assessment Area 5 (SEA5): Seabed and superficial geology and processes. British Geological Survey Report CR/04/064N. BGS, Edinburgh.
- 12 Brooks, A.J., Kenyon, N.H., Leslie, A., Long, D. & Gordon, J.E. 2011. Characterising Scotland's marine environment to define search locations for new Marine Protected Areas. Part 2: The identification of key geodiversity areas in Scottish waters (interim report July 2011). Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 430 (Project no. 28877).
- 13 Eleftheriou, A., Basford, D.J. & Moore, D.C. 2004. Synthesis of Information on the Benthos of Area SEA 5. Report for the Department of Trade and Industry.
- 14 Greathead, C., Demain, D., Dobby, H., Allan, L. & Weetman, A. 2011. Quantitative assessment of the distribution and abundance of the burrowing megafauna and large epifauna community in the Fladen fishing ground, northern North Sea. *Scottish Marine and Freshwater Science*, 2(2). Marine Scotland – Science. 23 pp.
- 15 Scottish Natural Heritage. 2014. Further advice to Scottish Government on the selection of Nature Conservation Marine Protected Areas for the development of the Scottish MPA network. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 780.
- 16 MacDonald, D.S., Little, M., Eno, N.C. & Hiscock, K. 1996. Disturbance of benthic species by fishing activities: a sensitivity index. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 6: 257-268.
- 17 Moore, C.G. 2017. Biological analyses of underwater video from ongoing monitoring and research cruises in Lochs Sunart, Etive and Alsh, sea lochs off South Skye, the Sounds of Barra and Arisaig and around the Southern Trench. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 959.
- 18 Moore, C.G. 2019. Biological analyses of underwater video from monitoring and research cruises in Lochs Ailort and Fyne, the Sounds of Barra and Mull, inner Moray Firth, off Wester Ross, Noss Head and Rattray Head, and around the Southern Trench in outer Moray Firth. Scottish Natural Heritage Research Report No. 1085.
- 19 Pearce, B., Hill, J.M., Wilson, C., Griffin, R., Earnshaw, S. & Pitts, J. 2011. *Sabellaria spinulosa* Reef Ecology and Ecosystem Services. The Crown Estate. 120 pp.

- 20 Bruno, J.F. & M.D. Bertness. 2001. Habitat modification and facilitation in benthic marine communities. In: *Marine Community Ecology*, pp. 201-218. Bertness, M.D., Gaines, S.D., & Hay, M.E. (eds.). Sinauer Associates, Sunderland, MA.
- 21 Hirst, N.E., Clark, L. & Sanderson, W.G. 2012. The distribution of selected MPA search features and Priority Marine Features off the NE coast of Scotland. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No.500.
- 22 MMT. 2013. Environmental Survey Report. Hywind Offshore Windfarm. Statoil Doc. No: ST13828 Benthic Report. MMT Doc. No: 101462-STO-MMT-SUR-REP-ENVIRON. Petersen, Scotland. 74 pp.
- 23 Axelsson, M., O'Dell, J. & Dewey, S. 2017. Infaunal and PSA analyses of benthic samples collected from South Arran MPA, Lochs Duich, Long and Alsh MPA and Southern Trench MPA proposal. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 946.
- 24 Tyler-Walters, H., James, B., Carruthers, M. (eds.), Wilding, C., Durkin, O., Lacey, C., Philpott, E., Adams, L., Chaniotis, P.D., Wilkes, P.T.V., Seeley, R., Neilly M., Dargie, J. & Crawford-Avis, O.T. 2016. Descriptions of Scottish Priority Marine Features (PMFs). Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 406.
- 25 Mann, K.H. 1973. Seaweeds: their productivity and strategy for growth. *Science*, 182(4116): 975-981.
- 26 Steneck, R.S., Graham, M.H., Bourque, B.J., Corbett, D., Erlandson, J.M., Estes, J.A. & Tegner, M.J. 2002. Kelp forest ecosystems: biodiversity, stability, resilience and future. *Environmental Conservation*, 29(4): 436-459.
- 27 Tegner, M.J. & Dayton, P.K. 2000. Ecosystem effects of fishing in kelp forest communities. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 57(3): 579-589.
- 28 Christie, H., Jørgensen, N.M., Norderhaug, K.M. & Waage-Nielsen, E. 2003. Species distribution and habitat exploitation of fauna associated with kelp (*Laminaria hyperborea*) along the Norwegian coast. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 83(4): 687-699.
- 29 Norderhaug, K.M., Christie, H., Fosså, J.H. & Fredriksen, S. 2005. Fish-macrofauna interactions in a kelp (*Laminaria hyperborea*) forest. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 85(5): 1279-1286.
- 30 Smale, D.A., Burrows, M.T., Moore, P., O'Connor, N. & Hawkins S.J. 2013. Threats and knowledge gaps for ecosystem services provided by kelp forests: a northeast Atlantic perspective. *Ecology and Evolution*, 3(11): 4016-4038.
- 31 Yesson, C., Bush, L.E., Davies, A.J., Maggs, C.A., & Brodie, J. 2015. Large brown seaweeds of the British Isles: evidence of changes in abundance over four decades. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 155: 167-175.
- 32 Belkin, I.M., Cornillon, P.C., & Sherman, K. 2009. Fronts in large marine ecosystems. *Progress in Oceanography*, 81(1-4): 223-236.
- 33 Miller, P.I., Xu, W., Lonsdale, P. 2014. Seasonal shelf-sea front mapping using satellite ocean colour to support development of the Scottish MPA network. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 538.
- 34 Paxton, C.G., Scott-Hayward, L.A.S., & Rexstad, E.A. 2014. Statistical approaches to aid the identification of Marine Protected Areas for minke whale, Risso's dolphin, white-beaked dolphin and basking shark. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 594.
- 35 Tetley, M.J., Mitchelson-Jacob, E.G. & Robinson, K.P. 2008. The summer distribution of coastal minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) in the southern outer Moray Firth, NE Scotland, in relation to co-occurring mesoscale oceanographic features. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 112(8): 3449-3454.
- 36 Robinson, K.P., Baumgartner, N., Eisfeld, S.M., Clark, N.M., Culloch, R.M., Haskins, G.N., Zapponi, L., Whaley, A.R., Weare, J.S. & Tetley, M.J. 2007. The summer distribution and occurrence of cetaceans in the coastal waters of the outer southern Moray Firth in northeast Scotland (UK). *Lutra*, 50(1): 19-30.
- 37 Ellis, J.R., Milligan, S.P., Readdy, L., Taylor, N. & M.J. Brown. 2012. Spawning and nursery grounds of selected fish species in UK waters. *Science Series Technical Report No. 147*. Cefas, Lowestoft. 56 pp.
- 38 Sundby, S., Kristiansen, T., Nash, R. & Johannessen, T. 2017. Dynamic Mapping of North Sea Spawning - Report of the KINO Project. Havforskninginstituttet, Bergen. 195 pp.
- 39 STECF. 2006. Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries opinion on 'sensitive and essential fish habitats in the Mediterranean Sea'. Commission staff working paper. Rome. 48 pp.
- 40 Sponaugle, S., Cowen, R.K., Shanks, A., Morgan, S.G., Leis, J.M., Pineda, J., Boehlert, G.W., Kingsford, M.J., Lindeman, K.C., Grimes, C. & Munro, J.L. 2002. Predicting self-recruitment in marine populations: biophysical correlates and mechanisms. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 70(1): 341-375.

- 41 Stephen, A.C. 1923. Preliminary survey of the Scottish waters of the North Sea by the Petersen grab. Fisheries Board for Scotland, *Scientific Investigations*, 1922 (No III): 1-21.
- 42 Kingston, P.F. & Harries, D. 2000. UK Benthos: Database of offshore Environmental benthic surveys in the UK sector of the North Sea. UKOOA Ltd.
- 43 Allan, L., Demain, D., Weetman, A., Dobby H. & McLay, A. 2012. Data Mining of the Nephrops Survey Database to Support the Scottish MPA Project. *Scottish Marine and Freshwater Science*, 3, p.35.
- 44 Stephen, A.C. 1933. Studies on the Scottish marine fauna: the natural faunistic divisions of the North Sea as shown by the quantitative distribution of the molluscs. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*, 57: 601-616.
- 45 Stephen, A.C. 1934. Studies on the Scottish marine fauna: quantitative distributions of the echinoderms and natural faunistic divisions of the North Sea. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*, 57: 777-787.
- 46 McIntyre, A.D. (1958). The ecology of Scottish inshore fishing grounds. The bottom fauna of east coast grounds. *Marine Research*, 1: 1-24.
- 47 Eleftheriou, A. & Basford, D.J. 1989. The macrofaunal infauna of the offshore northern North Sea. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 69: 123-143.
- 48 Heip, C., Huys, R., Vincx, M.M., Vanreusel, A., Smol, N., Herman, R. & Herman, P.M.J. 1990. Composition, distribution, biomass and production of North Sea meiofauna. *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research*, 26: 333-342.
- 49 Heip, C., Basford, D., Craeymeersch, J.A., Dewaromez, J.M., Dörjes, J., de Wilde, P., Duineveld, G., Eleftheriou, A., Herman, P.M.J., Niermann, U., Kingston, P., Künitzer, A., Rador, E., Rumohr, H., Soetaert, K. & Soltwedel, K. 1992. Trends in biomass, density and diversity of North Sea macrofauna. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 49(1): 13-22.
- 50 Künitzer, A., Basford, D.J., Craeymeersch, J.M., Dewaromez, J.M., Dörjes, J., Eleftheriou, A., Heip, C., Herman, P.M., Kingston, P., Niermann, U., Rumohr, H. & De Wilde, P.A.J. 1992. The benthic infauna of the North Sea: species distribution and assemblages. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 49(2): 127-143.
- 51 Duineveld, G.C.A., Künitzer, A., Niermann, U., De Wilde, P.A.W.J. & Gray, J.S. 1991. The macrobenthos of the North Sea. *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research*, 28: 53-65.
- 52 Dyer, M.F., Fry, W.G., Fry, P.D. & Cranmer, G.J. 1982. A series of North Sea benthos surveys with trawl and headline camera. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 62(2): 297-313.
- 53 Dyer, M.F., Fry, W.G., Fry P.D. & Cranmer, G.J. 1983. Benthic regions within the North Sea. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 63(3): 683-693.
- 54 Cranmer, G.J. 1985. Recent investigations into the distribution of regular echinoids in the North Sea. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 65(2): 351-357.
- 55 ICES. 2019. Manual for the International Bottom Trawl Surveys. Series of ICES Survey Protocols. SISP 10, Version 10. 86 pp. <http://doi.org/10.17895/ices.pub.5713>
- 56 Huys, R., Herman, P.M.J., Heip, C.H.R. & Soetaert, K. 1990. The meiobenthos of the North Sea: Preliminary results of the North Sea benthos survey. ICES CM 1990/Mini:8. 16 pp.
- 57 Huys, R., Herman P.M.J., Heip, C.H.R. & Soetaert, K. (1992). The meiobenthos of the North Sea: density biomass trends and distribution of copepod communities. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 49: 23-44.
- 58 Jennings, S., Lancaster, J., Woolmer, A. & Cotter, J. 1999. Distribution, diversity and abundance of epibenthic fauna in the North Sea. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 79: 385-399.
- 59 Scottish Natural Heritage. 2014. Scottish MPA Project. Data confidence assessment. Southern Trench MPA Proposal. Available from: <https://www.nature.scot/sites/default/files/2017-11/Marine%20Protected%20Area%20-%20Data%20confidence%20assessment%20-%20Southern%20Trench%20MPA%20proposal.pdf>
- 60 Eleftheriou, A. & Robertson, M. R. 1992. The effects of experimental scallop dredging on the fauna and physical environment of a shallow sandy community. *Netherlands Journal of Sea Research*, 30: 289-299.
- 61 Veale, L.O., Hill, A.S., Hawkins, S.J. & Brand, A.R. 2001. Distribution and damage to the by-catch assemblages of the northern Irish Sea scallop dredge fisheries. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 81(1): 85-96.
- 62 Jennings, S. & Kaiser, M.J. 1998. The effects of fishing on marine ecosystems. In: *Advances in Marine Biology*, Vol 34, pp. 203-354. Blaxter, J.H.S., Southward, A.J. & Tyler, P.A. (eds). London: Academic Press.

- 63 ICES. 2016. Fishing Effort Datasets. Scottish Government. Riaghaltas na h-Alba gov.scot. Available from: <https://www2.gov.scot/Topics/Statistics/Browse/Agriculture-Fisheries/RectangleData/2016FishingEffortDatasetsICES>
- 64 ICES. 2016. Quantity and Value table. Scottish Government. Riaghaltas na h-Alba gov.scot. Available from: <http://www.gov.scot/Topics/Statistics/Browse/Agriculture-Fisheries/RectangleData/2016QuantityandValuetableICES>
- 65 ICES. 2016. ICES Statistical Rectangles and Areas. Scottish Government. Riaghaltas na h-Alba gov.scot. Available from: <http://marine.gov.scot/maps/46>
- 66 Davies, J.M., Addy, J.M., Blackman, R.A., Blanchard, J.R., Ferbrache, J.E., Moore, D.C., Somerville, H.J., Whitehead, A. & Wilkinson, T. 1984. Environmental effects of the use of oil-based drilling muds in the North Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 15(10): 363-370.
- 67 Gray, J.S., Clarke, K.R., Warwick, R.M. & Hobbs, G. 1990. Detection of initial effects of pollution on marine benthos: an example from the Ekofisk and Eldfisk oilfields, North Sea. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 66: 285-299.
- 68 Cordes, E.E., Jones, D.O.B., Schlacher, T.A., Amon, D.J., Bernardino, A.F., Brooke, S., Carney, R., DeLeo, D.M., Dunlop, K.M., Escobar-Briones, E.G., Gates, A.R., Génio, L., Gobin, J., Henry, L.A., Herrera, S., Hoyt, S., Joye, M., Kark, S., Mestre, N.C., Metaxas, A., Pfeifer, S., Sink, K., Sweetman, A.K. & Witte, U. 2016. Environmental Impacts of the Deep-Water Oil and Gas Industry: A Review to Guide Management Strategies. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 4:58.
- 69 Kingston, P.F. 1992. Impact of offshore oil production installations on the benthos of the North Sea. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 49(1): 45-53.
- 70 Dixon, T. 2015. Annual survey of reported discharges and releases attributed to vessels and offshore oil and gas installations operating in the United Kingdom's exclusive economic zone (UK EEZ) 2014. Advisory Committee on Protection of the Sea, Cambridge. Available from: <http://www.acops.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/ACOPS-Annual-Pollution-Survey-2014.pdf>
- 71 Oil and Gas Authority. 2019. Available from: <https://data-ogauthority.opendata.arcgis.com/search?tags=Zip>
- 72 TeleGeography. 2019. Submarine cable map. Available from: www.submarinecablemap.com/#/
- 73 The Crown Estate. Personal communication, Kieran Bell (GIS Lead – Energy, Minerals & Infrastructure).
- 74 4C Offshore. 2019. Offshore wind. <https://www.4coffshore.com/offshorewind/>
- 75 Marine Scotland. 2015. MAPS NMPi. Dredge Spoil Disposal Sites – Open. Available from: <https://marinescotland.atkinsgeospatial.com/nmpi/default.aspx?layers=712>
- 76 Marine Scotland. 2015. MAPS NMPi. Dredge Spoil Disposal Sites - Closed and Disused. Available from: <https://marinescotland.atkinsgeospatial.com/nmpi/default.aspx?layers=717>
- 77 Marine Scotland. 2019. Draft Sectoral Marine Plan for Offshore Wind Energy (2019). Available from: <http://www.gov.scot/ISBN/9781839603747>
- 78 Hiscock, K., Tyler-Walters, H. & Jones, H. 2002. High Level Environmental Screening Study for Offshore Wind Farm Developments – Marine Habitats and Species Project. Report from the Marine Biological Association to The Department of Trade and Industry New & Renewable Energy Programme.
- 79 Gill, A.B. 2005. Offshore renewable energy: ecological implications of generating electricity in the coastal zone. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 42(4): 605-615.
- 80 Carstensen, J., Henriksen, O.D. & Teilmann, J. 2006. Impacts of offshore wind farm construction on harbour porpoises: acoustic monitoring of echolocation activity using porpoise detectors (T-PODs). *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 321: 295-308.
- 81 Bailey, H., Senior, B., Simmons, D., Rusin, J., Picken, G. & Thompson, P.M. 2010. Assessing underwater noise levels during pile-driving at an offshore windfarm and its potential effects on marine mammals. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 60(6): 888-897.
- 82 Brandt, M.J., Diederichs, A., Betke, K. & Nehls, G. 2011. Responses of harbour porpoises to pile driving at the Horns Rev II offshore wind farm in the Danish North Sea. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 421: 205-216.
- 83 Jambeck, J.R., Geyer, R., Wilcox, C., Siegler, T.R., Perryman, M., Andrady, A., Narayan, R. & Law, K.L. 2015. Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean. *Science*, 347(6223): 768-771.
- 84 Kammann, U., Aust, M.O., Bahl, H. & Lang, T. 2018. Marine litter at the seafloor – Abundance and composition in the North Sea and the Baltic Sea. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 127: 774-780.
- 85 Foekema, E.M., De Gruijter, C., Mergia, M.T., van Franeker, J.A., Murk A.J. & Koelmans, A.A. 2013. Plastic in North Sea fish. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 47(15): 8818-8824.

- 86 Thompson, R.C. 2015. Microplastics in the Marine Environment: Sources, Consequences and Solutions. In: *Marine Anthropogenic Litter*, pp. 185-200. Bergmann, M., Gutow, L. & Klages, M. (eds.) Springer, Cham.
- 87 European Environment Agency (EEA). Natura 2000 Network Viewer. Available from: <http://natura2000.eea.europa.eu/2019>
- 88 Bigné, M., Nielsen, J.R. & Bastardie, F. 2018. Opening of the Norway pout box: will it change the ecological impacts of the North Sea Norway pout fishery? *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 76: 136-152.
- 89 Greenstreet, S., Fraser, H., Armstrong, E. & Gibb, I. 2010. Monitoring the Consequences of the Northwestern North Sea Sandeel Fishery Closure. *Scottish Marine and Freshwater Science*, 1(6). Marine Scotland – Science. 31 pp.
- 90 JNCC. 2018. Turbot Bank MPA. Available from: <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/turbot-bank-mpa/>
- 91 JNCC. 2018. Firth of Forth Banks Complex MPA. Available from: <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/firth-of-forth-banks-complex-mpa/>
- 92 Scottish Natural Heritage. 2019. Natural spaces. Available from: <http://gateway.snh.gov.uk/natural-spaces/index.jsp>
- 93 Wright, P., Verspoor, E., Anderson, C., Donald, L., Kennedy, F., Mitchell, A., Munk, P., Pedersen, S.A., Jensen H., Gislason, H., and Lewy, P. 1998. Population structure in the lesser sandeel (*Ammodytes marinus*) and its implications for fishery-predator interactions. Final report to DG XIV 94/C 144/ 04. Study Proposal No. 94/071.
- 94 Marine (Scotland) Act 2010 (asp 5). Available from: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2010/5/contents>
- 95 WDCS, HWDT and CRRU. 2012. Third Party Proposal Submission to the Scottish MPA Project. Available from: <https://docplayer.net/21210004-Third-party-proposal-submission-to-the-scottish-mpa-project-i.html>
- 96 Scottish Natural Heritage and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee. 2012. Advice to the Scottish Government on the selection of Nature Conservation Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) for the development of the Scottish MPA network. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 547
- 97 Tyler-Walters, H., James, B. (eds.), Wilding, C., Durkin, O., Lacey, C., Philpott, E., Adams, L., Chaniotis, P.D., Wilkes, P.T.V., Seeley, R., Neilly, M., Dargie, J. & Crawford-Avis, O.T. 2012. Descriptions of Marine Protected Area (MPA) search features. A report produced by MarLIN (Marine Life Information Network), SMRU Ltd., Scottish Natural Heritage and the Joint Nature Conservation Committee, for the Scottish Marine Protected Areas Project.
- 98 Scottish Natural Heritage. 2014. Further advice to Scottish Government on the selection of Nature Conservation Marine Protected Areas for the development of the Scottish MPA network. Scottish Natural Heritage Commissioned Report No. 780.
- 99 Cunningham, S., Chaniotis, P.D., Gillham, K. & James, B. 2015. Assessment of the adequacy of the Scottish MPA network for MPA search features: summary of the application of stage 5 of the MPA Selection Guidelines post consultation. Assessing risk to Scottish MPA search features at the MPA regional scale. Final report produced by the Joint Nature Conservation Committee, Scottish Natural Heritage and Marine Scotland for the Scottish Marine Protected Areas Project.
- 100 Scottish Environment LINK. 2018. Marine: Scottish Parliament votes to support iconic mobile species. 31 January 2018. Available from: <https://www.scotlink.org/marine-scottish-parliament-votes-to-support-iconic-mobile-species/>
- 101 Scottish Government. 2019. Protected areas for mobile marine species: consultation on proposals to designate four new Marine Protected Areas in Scottish waters. Marine Scotland Directorate. Available from: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/marine-protected-areas-mobile-marine-species-consultation-proposals-designate-four-new-marine-protected-areas-scottish-waters/>
- 102 Scottish Natural Heritage and Marine Scotland. 2019. Southern Trench: Possible Marine Protected Area. Available from: <https://www.nature.scot/sites/default/files/2019-06/Southern Trench possible MPA - Site Summary Leaflet.pdf>
- 103 Scottish Natural Heritage. 2019. Scottish MPA Programme Assessment against the MPA Selection Guidelines. Southern Trench Possible MPA. Available from: <https://www.nature.scot/sites/default/files/2019-06/Southern Trench possible MPA - Application of the MPA Selection Guidelines.pdf>
- 104 Marine Scotland. 2019. A consultation on proposals to designate four Marine Protected Areas in Scottish waters. Published responses. Available from: https://consult.gov.scot/marine-scotland/four-new-marine-protected-areas/consultation/view_respondent?show_all_questions=0&sort=submitted&order=ascending&q_text=oceana&uuld=833006390
- 105 Davies, C.E., Moss, D. & Hill, M.O. 2004. EUNIS habitat classification revised 2004. Report to: European Environment Agency-European Topic Centre on Nature Protection and Biodiversity, pp. 127-143.

- 106 OSPAR Commission. 2008. OSPAR List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats (Reference Number: 2008-6). Available from: <https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/bdc/species-habitats/list-of-threatened-declining-species-habitats>
- 107 EEC. 1992. Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora. Annex II: Animal and plant species of Community interest whose conservation requires the designation of Special Areas of Conservation. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 206, 22.7.1992.
- 108 ICES. 2016. Report of the Workshop on Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem Database (WKVME), 10-11 December 2015, Peterborough, UK. ICES CM 2015/ACOM:62. 42 pp.
- 109 Scottish Natural Heritage. 2013. Scottish Biodiversity List. Available from: <https://www.nature.scot/scotlands-biodiversity/scottish-biodiversity-strategy/scottish-biodiversity-list>
- 110 Marine Scotland, Scottish Natural Heritage & JNCC. 2011. Marine Protected Areas in Scotland's Seas. Guidelines on the selection of MPAs and development of the MPA network. Available from: <https://www2.gov.scot/Resource/0051/00515466.pdf>
- 111 Butler, P.G., Wanamaker, A.D., Scourse, J.D., Richardson, C.A. & Reynolds, D.J. 2013. Variability of marine climate on the North Icelandic Shelf in a 1357-year proxy archive based on growth increments in the bivalve *Arctica islandica*. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 373: 141-151.
- 112 OSPAR Commission. 2009. Background Document for ocean quahog *Arctica islandica*. Biodiversity Series. Publication Number: 407/2009. OSPAR Commission, London, UK. Available from: <https://www.ospar.org/documents?d=7171>
- 113 OSPAR Commission. 2013. Background document on *Sabellaria spinulosa* reefs. Biodiversity Series. Publication Number: 614/2013. OSPAR Commission, London, UK. Available from: <https://www.ospar.org/documents?v=7342>
- 114 Gravina, M.F., Cardone, F., Bonifazi, A., Bertrandino, M.S., Chimienti, G., Longo, C., Nonnis Marzano, C., Moretti, M., Lisco, S., Moretti, V., Corriero, G. & Giangrande, A. 2018. *Sabellaria spinulosa* (Polychaeta, Annelida) reefs in the Mediterranean Sea: Habitat mapping, dynamics and associated fauna for conservation management. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 200: 248-257.
- 115 Chapman, N. (Ed.) 2011. *Sabellaria spinulosa* Reefs. In: Maddock, A. (ed.). UK Biodiversity Action Plan: Priority Habitat Descriptions. Biodiversity Reporting and Information Group. Available from: http://jncc.defra.gov.uk/PDF/UKBAP_PriorityHabitatDesc-Rev2011.pdf
- 116 European Commission. 2013. Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats. EUR 28. DG Environment, European Commission. Available from: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/habitatsdirective/docs/Int_Manual_EU28.pdf
- 117 OSPAR Commission. 2010. Quality Status Report. *Sabellaria spinulosa* reefs. OSPAR Commission, London, UK. Available from: https://qsr2010.ospar.org/media/assessments/Species/p0010_supplements/CH10_04_Sabellaria_spinulosa.pdf
- 118 OSPAR Commission. 2010. Background document for seapen and burrowing megafauna communities. Biodiversity Series. Publication Number: 481/2010. Available from: <https://www.ospar.org/documents?d=7261>
- 119 Bergstad, O.A., Høines, A.S. & Krüger-Johnsen, E.M. 2001. Spawning time, age and size at maturity, and fecundity of sandeel, *Ammodytes marinus*, in the north-eastern North Sea and in unfished coastal waters off Norway. *Aquatic Living Resources*, 14: 293-301.
- 120 ICES. 2019. Cod (*Gadus morhua*) in Subarea 4, Division 7.d, and Subdivision 20 (North Sea, eastern English Channel, Skagerrak). ICES Advice on fishing opportunities. Greater North Sea ecoregion. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.advice.5640>
- 121 ICES. 2019. Haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) in Subarea 4, Division 6.a, and Subdivision 20 (North Sea, West of Scotland, Skagerrak). ICES Advice on fishing opportunities. Celtic Seas and Greater North Sea ecoregion. Available from: http://ices.dk/sites/pub/Publication%20Reports/Advice/2019/2019/had.27.46a20_replaced.pdf
- 122 ICES. 2019. Whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*) in Subarea 4 and Division 7.d (North Sea and eastern English Channel). ICES Advice on fishing opportunities. Greater North Sea ecoregion. Available from: <http://ices.dk/sites/pub/Publication%20Reports/Advice/2019/2019/whg.27.47d.pdf>
- 123 Coull, K.A., Johnstone, R. & Rogers, S.I. 1998. Fisheries Sensitivity Maps in British Waters. Published and distributed by UKOOA Ltd. 58 pp.
- 124 Marine Scotland. 2019. Marine Scotland MAPS NMPi (National Marine Plan interactive). <https://marinescotland.atkinsgeospatial.com/nmpi/default.aspx?layers=654>
- 125 OSPAR Commission. 2013. Recommendation 2013/2 on furthering the protection and conservation of *Sabellaria spinulosa* reefs in Regions II and III of the OSPAR maritime area. OSPAR 13/4/1, Annex 5. Available from: <https://www.ospar.org/documents?d=32964>

© OCEANA/ Juan Cueto

ANNEX: RECORDED TAXA

Table A. Taxa documented in Aberdeenshire during the Oceana North Sea expedition in 2017.

Species
Chlorophyta
<i>Cladophora rupestris</i>
<i>Cladophora</i> sp.
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>
<i>Ulva</i> sp.
Rhodophyta
<i>Calliblepharis ciliata</i>
<i>Ceramium virgatum</i>
<i>Cystoclonium purpureum</i>
<i>Delesseria sanguinea</i>
<i>Dilsea carnososa</i>
<i>Heterosiphonia plumosa</i>
<i>Jania rubens</i>
<i>Palmaria palmata</i>
<i>Phycodrys rubens</i>
<i>Phymatolithon lenormandii</i>
<i>Plocamium cartilagineum</i>
<i>Polysiphonia</i> sp.
<i>Porphyra</i> sp.
Rhodophyta indet.
Ochrophyta
<i>Alaria esculenta</i>
<i>Desmarestia aculeata</i>
<i>Desmarestia ligulata</i>
<i>Desmarestia viridis</i>
<i>Dictyota dichotoma</i>
<i>Fucus serratus</i>
<i>Fucus</i> sp.
<i>Laminaria hyperborea</i>
<i>Laminaria</i> sp.
<i>Leathesia marina</i>

Ochrophyta indet.
<i>Saccharina latissima</i>
<i>Undaria pinnatifida</i>
Annelida
<i>Amphictene auricoma</i>
cf. <i>Amphilectene auricoma</i>
Annelida indet.
<i>Arenicola marina</i>
<i>Bonellia viridis</i>
<i>Chaetopterus</i> sp.
<i>Chone fauveli</i>
<i>Filograna implexa</i>
<i>Hediste diversicolor</i>
<i>Hyalinoecia tubicola</i>
<i>Hydroides norvegica</i>
<i>Lagis</i> cf. <i>koreni</i>
<i>Lagis koreni</i>
<i>Lanice conchilega</i>
<i>Mysta picta</i>
<i>Nephtys</i> sp.
<i>Ophelia limacina</i>
<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>
Polychaeta indet.
<i>Pomatoceros</i> sp.
<i>Pomatoceros triqueter</i>
<i>Pyllodoce maculata</i>
<i>Sabella pavonina</i>
<i>Sabella</i> sp.
<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i>
Serpulidae indet.
<i>Spirorbis</i> sp.
<i>Spirobranchus triqueter</i>

Arthropoda
<i>Achaeus cranchi</i>
<i>Ampelisca spinipes</i>
Amphipoda indet.
Anomura indet.
<i>Astacilla longicornis</i>
<i>Atelecyclus rotundatus</i>
<i>Balanus balanus</i>
<i>Balanus crenatus</i>
<i>Balanus</i> sp.
<i>Bathyporeia</i> sp.
<i>Bodotria scorpioides</i>
<i>Cancer pagurus</i>
<i>Carcinus maenas</i>
Caridea indet.
<i>Corystes casivelaunus</i>
<i>Crangon crangon</i>
Decapoda indet.
<i>Ebalia</i> sp.
<i>Eualus cranchii</i>
<i>Eualus gaimardii</i>
<i>Eualus pusiolus</i>
<i>Eualus</i> sp.
Euphasiacea indet.
<i>Galathea intermedia</i>
<i>Galathea nexa</i>
<i>Galathea</i> sp.
<i>Galathea squamifera</i>
<i>Galathea strigosa</i>
<i>Homarus gammarus</i>
<i>Hyas araneus</i>
<i>Hyas coarctatus</i>

<i>Hyas</i> sp.
<i>Idotea</i> sp.
<i>Inachus dorsettensis</i>
<i>Inachus</i> sp.
<i>Iphimedia obesus</i>
<i>Lebbeus polaris</i>
<i>Liocarcinus depurator</i>
<i>Liocarcinus marmoratus</i>
<i>Liocarcinus pusillus</i>
<i>Liocarcinus</i> sp.
<i>Lithodes maja</i>
<i>Macropodia rostrata</i>
<i>Macropodia</i> sp.
<i>Munida rugosa</i>
<i>Munida sarsi</i>
<i>Munida</i> sp.
<i>Necora puber</i>
cf. <i>Owenia fusiformis</i>
<i>Pagurus bernhardus</i>
<i>Pagurus prideaux</i>
<i>Pagurus pubescens</i>
<i>Pagurus</i> sp.
<i>Pandalina brevirostris</i>
<i>Pandalus borealis</i>
<i>Pandalus montagui</i>
<i>Pandalus</i> sp.
<i>Pariambus typicus</i>
<i>Pisa tetraodon</i>
<i>Pisidia longicornis</i>
<i>Polybius henslowi</i>
<i>Scalpellum scalpellum</i>
<i>Semibalanus balanoides</i>

<i>Spirontocaris liljeborgii</i>
<i>Stenopleustes latipes</i>
<i>Strobopagurus gracilipes</i>
Bryozoa
<i>Alcyonidium diaphanum</i>
<i>Alcyonidium hirsutum</i>
<i>Alcyonidium</i> sp.
Bryozoa indet.
<i>Bugula flabellata</i>
<i>Caberea ellisii</i>
<i>Caberea</i> sp.
<i>Cellaria sinuosa</i>
<i>Cellaria</i> sp.
<i>Conopeum reticulum</i>
<i>Crisia</i> cf. <i>eburnean</i>
<i>Crisia</i> sp.
<i>Electra monotaschys</i>
<i>Electra pilosa</i>
<i>Escharella variolosa</i>
<i>Escharina johnstoni</i>
<i>Escharoides coccinea</i>
<i>Exidmonea atlantica</i>
<i>Flustra foliacea</i>
<i>Membranipora membranacea</i>
<i>Omalosecosa ramulosa</i>
<i>Parasmittina</i> sp.
<i>Parasmittina trispinosa</i>
<i>Plagioecia patina</i>
<i>Porella</i> sp.
<i>Reteporella beaniana</i>
<i>Schizobrachiella sanguinea</i>
<i>Schizomavella</i> cf. <i>auriculata</i>

<i>Schizomavella linearis</i>
<i>Schizomavella</i> sp.
<i>Securiflustra securifrons</i>
<i>Smittoidea prolifica</i>
<i>Tubulipora liliacea</i>
<i>Turbicellepora avicularis</i>
<i>Turbicellepora magnicostata</i>
Chaetognatha
<i>Parasagitta elegans</i>
Chordata - Aves
<i>Alca torda</i>
<i>Fratercula arctica</i>
<i>Phalacrocorax aristotelis</i>
<i>Phalacrocorax</i> sp.
<i>Uria aalge</i>
Chordata - Mammalia
<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>
<i>Phoca</i> sp. (skull)
Chordata - Pisces
<i>Agonus cataphractus</i>
<i>Ammodytes marinus</i>
<i>Ammodytes</i> sp.
<i>Ammodytes tobianus</i>
<i>Aphia minuta</i>
<i>Arnoglossus laterna</i>
<i>Callionymus maculatus</i>
<i>Callionymus</i> sp.
<i>Chelidonichthys cuculus</i>
<i>Chirolophis ascanii</i>
Cottidae indet.
Gadidae indet.
<i>Gadus morhua</i>

<i>Hyperoplus lanceolatus</i>
<i>Labrus mixtus</i>
<i>Limanda limanda</i>
<i>Liparis liparis</i>
<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i>
<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>
<i>Microstomus kitt</i>
<i>Molva molva</i>
<i>Myoxocephalus scorpius</i>
<i>Myxine glutinosa</i>
<i>Pholis gunnellus</i>
<i>Phrynorhombus norvegicus</i>
Pisces indet.
Pleuronectiformes indet.
<i>Pollachius virens</i>
<i>Taurulus bubalis</i>
<i>Triglops murrayi</i>
<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>
<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>
Chordata - Tunicata
<i>Aplidium punctum</i>
<i>Aplidium</i> sp.
<i>Ascidia conchilega</i>
<i>Ascidia mentula</i>
<i>Ascidia</i> sp.
<i>Ascidia virginea</i>
Ascidacea indet.
<i>Ascidella aspersa</i>
<i>Ascidella scabra</i>
<i>Botrylloides leachii</i>
<i>Botrylloides</i> sp.
<i>Botryllus schlosseri</i>

<i>Botryllus</i> sp.
<i>Ciona intestinalis</i>
<i>Clavelina lepadiformis</i>
<i>Clavelina</i> sp.
<i>Corella parallelogramma</i>
<i>Dendrodoa grossularia</i>
<i>Didemnum</i> sp.
<i>Molgula manhattensis</i>
<i>Polycarpa pomaria</i>
Cnidaria
<i>Abietinaria abietina</i>
<i>Adamsi palliata</i>
<i>Aglaophenia pluma</i>
<i>Alcyonium digitatum</i>
<i>Caryophyllia smithii</i>
<i>Cerianthus lloydii</i>
<i>Cerianthus membranaceus</i>
<i>Cerianthus</i> sp.
<i>Clytia linearis</i>
<i>Cyanea capillata</i>
<i>Cyanea lamarckii</i>
<i>Diphasia rosacea</i>
cf. <i>Diphasia rosea</i>
<i>Dynamena pusilla</i>
<i>Ectopleura larynx</i>
<i>Eudendrium capillare</i>
<i>Eudendrium rameum</i>
<i>Eudendrium</i> sp.
<i>Halecium halecinum</i>
<i>Halecium plumosum</i>
<i>Halecium</i> sp.
<i>Hydrallmania falcata</i>

Hydrozoa indet.
<i>Kirchenpaueria pinnata</i>
<i>Lafoea dumosa</i>
<i>Litocarpia myriophyllum</i>
<i>Metridium senile</i>
<i>Nemertesia antennina</i>
<i>Nemertesia ramosa</i>
<i>Obelia</i> cf. <i>bidentata</i>
<i>Obelia geniculata</i>
<i>Pachycerianthus multiplicatus</i>
<i>Pennatula phosphorea</i>
<i>Polyplumaria flabellata</i>
<i>Rhizocaulus verticillatus</i>
<i>Sagartia elegans</i>
<i>Schizotricha frutescens</i>
<i>Sertularella gayi</i>
<i>Sertularia argentea</i>
<i>Stomphia coccinea</i>
<i>Thuiaria thuja</i>
<i>Tubularia indivisa</i>
<i>Urticina eques</i>
<i>Urticina felina</i>
<i>Urticina</i> sp.
Ctenophora
<i>Beroe cucumis</i>
<i>Bolinopsis infundibulum</i>
Echinodermata
<i>Amphiura chiajei</i>
<i>Amphiura filiformis</i>
<i>Antedon bifida</i>
<i>Asterias rubens</i>
Asteroidea indet.

<i>Astropecten irregularis</i>
<i>Brissopsis lyrifera</i>
<i>Crossaster papposus</i>
<i>Echinocardium chordatum</i>
<i>Echinocardium flavescens</i>
<i>Echinus esculentus</i>
<i>Echinocyamus pusillus</i>
cf. <i>Halipterus</i> sp.
<i>Henricia</i> sp.
<i>Hippasteria phrygiana</i>
<i>Luida ciliaris</i>
<i>Luida sarsi</i>
<i>Marthasterias glacialis</i>
<i>Ophiactis balli</i>
cf. <i>Ophiactis</i> sp.
<i>Ophiocomina nigra</i>
<i>Ophiothrix fragilis</i>
<i>Ophiura albida</i>
<i>Ophiura ophiura</i>
Ophiuroidea indet.
<i>Stichastrella rosea</i>
cf. <i>Stomphia coccinea</i>
<i>Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis</i>
Foraminifera
<i>Astrorhiza limicola</i>
Foraminifera indet.
Mollusca
<i>Abra alba</i>
<i>Abra prismatica</i>
<i>Abra tenuis</i>
<i>Acanthocardia echinata</i>
<i>Acanthodoris pilosa</i>

<i>Acteon tornatilis</i>
<i>Aeolidia papillosa</i>
<i>Aequipecten opercularis</i>
<i>Anomia ephippium</i>
Anomiidae indet.
<i>Antalis entalis</i>
<i>Antalis vulgaris</i>
<i>Aplysia punctata</i>
<i>Aplysia</i> sp.
<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i>
<i>Arca tetragona</i>
<i>Archidoris</i> sp.
<i>Arcopagia crassa</i>
<i>Arctica islandica</i>
<i>Astarte</i> cf. <i>elliptica</i>
<i>Astarte elliptica</i>
<i>Astarte montagui</i>
<i>Astarte</i> sp.
<i>Astarte sulcata</i>
Bivalvia indet.
<i>Boreotrophon</i> cf. <i>truncatus</i>
<i>Boreotrophon truncatus</i>
Caenogastropoda indet.
<i>Calliostoma</i> sp.
<i>Calliostoma zizyphinum</i>
Cardiidae indet.
Cephalopoda indet. (eggs)
<i>Chamelea striatula</i>
<i>Chlamys islandica</i>
<i>Clausinella fasciata</i>
<i>Clelandella miliaris</i>
<i>Colus gracilis</i>

<i>Corbula gibba</i>
<i>Coryphella</i> sp.
<i>Ctena decussata</i>
<i>Cylichna cylindracea</i>
<i>Dendronotus</i> cf. <i>frondosus</i>
<i>Dentalium dentalis</i>
<i>Doris pseudoargus</i>
<i>Dosinia exoleta</i>
<i>Dosinia lupinus</i>
<i>Eledone cirrhosa</i>
<i>Emarginula fissura</i>
<i>Ennucula tenuis</i>
<i>Eubbranchus farrani</i>
<i>Eubbranchus pallidus</i>
<i>Eubbranchus tricolor</i>
<i>Eulimella ataktos</i>
<i>Euspira catena</i>
<i>Euspira nitida</i>
<i>Euspira</i> sp.
<i>Facelina auriculata</i>
<i>Facelina bostoniensis</i>
<i>Favorinus branchialis</i>
Gastropoda indet.
<i>Gari costulata</i>
<i>Gari fervensis</i>
<i>Gari tellinella</i>
<i>Gibbula cineraria</i>
<i>Gibbula</i> sp.
<i>Gibbula tumida</i>
<i>Gibbula umbilicalis</i>
<i>Glossus humanus</i>
<i>Glycimeris glycimeris</i>

<i>Gouldia minima</i>
cf. <i>Gouldia minima</i>
<i>Heteranomia squamula</i>
<i>Hiatella arctica</i>
<i>Janolus cristatus</i>
<i>Jorunna tomentosa</i>
<i>Lacuna</i> sp.
<i>Leptochiton asellus</i>
<i>Limaria loscombi</i>
<i>Limatula gwyni</i>
<i>Lucinoma borealis</i>
cf. <i>Lucinoma borealis</i>
<i>Macoma moesta</i>
<i>Mactra stultorum</i>
cf. <i>Mactra stultorum</i>
Mactridae indet.
<i>Mimachlamys varia</i>
<i>Modiolula phaseolina</i>
<i>Modiolus modiolus</i>
Muricidae indet.
<i>Mya arenaria</i>
<i>Nassarius pygmaeus</i>
<i>Nassarius reticulatus</i>
<i>Nassarius</i> sp.
cf. <i>Neilonella latior</i>
<i>Nucula</i> cf. <i>nucleus</i>
<i>Nucula nitidosa</i>
<i>Nucula nucleus</i>
<i>Nucula</i> sp.
<i>Nuculana minuta</i>
<i>Nuculana pernula</i>
Nudibranchia indet.

Nudibranchia indet. (eggs)
<i>Oenopota assimilis</i>
<i>Oenopota cf. assimilis</i>
<i>Oenopota cf. turricula</i>
<i>Oenopota turricula</i>
<i>Onchidoris bilamellata</i>
<i>Onchidoris luteocincta</i>
Ostreidae indet.
<i>Palliolium incomparabile</i>
<i>Palliolium striatum</i>
<i>Panomya norvegica</i>
<i>Parvicardium cf. pinnulatum</i>
<i>Parvicardium pinnatulum</i>
<i>Parvicardium scabrum</i>
<i>Patella pellucida</i>
<i>Patella sp.</i>
<i>Pecten maximus</i>
Patellogastropoda indet.
Pectinidae indet.
<i>Phaxas pellucidus</i>
<i>Pododesmus patelliformis</i>
<i>Pododesmus striata</i>
<i>Polycera faeroensis</i>
<i>Polycera quadrilineata</i>
<i>Propebela turricula</i>
<i>Pseudamussium peslutrae</i>
<i>Pyrgiscus crenatus</i>
<i>Raphitoma aequalis</i>
<i>Raphitoma sp.</i>
<i>Rissoa parva</i>
<i>Rissoa sp.</i>
Scaphopoda indet.

Semelidae indet.
<i>Similipecten similis</i>
<i>Simnia patula</i>
<i>Spisula elliptica</i>
<i>Spisula</i> sp.
<i>Spisula subtruncata</i>
<i>Tapes corrugata</i>
<i>Tapes philippinarum</i>
<i>Tectura virginea</i>
<i>Tellimya ferruginosa</i>
<i>Tellina</i> cf. <i>pygmaea</i>
<i>Tellina fabula</i>
<i>Tellina pygmaea</i>
<i>Tellina tenuis</i>
cf. <i>Tellimya tenella</i>
<i>Thracia phaseolina</i>
<i>Thracia</i> sp.
<i>Thracia villosiuscula</i>
<i>Thyasira flexuosa</i>
<i>Thyasira sarsi</i>
<i>Timoclea ovata</i>
<i>Tonicella marmorea</i>
<i>Tonicella rubra</i>
<i>Tritia incrassata</i>
<i>Tritia reticulatus</i>
<i>Tritonia hombergii</i>
<i>Trivia arctica</i>
<i>Trivia monacha</i>
<i>Turbonilla rufa</i>
<i>Turritella communis</i>
Raphistomidae indet.
Veneridae indet.

<i>Venus cassina</i>
<i>Venus verrucosa</i>
Platyhelminthes
Platyhelminthes indet.
Porifera
<i>Antho (Antho) dichotoma</i>
<i>Antho</i> sp.
Demospongiae indet.
<i>Dysidea fragilis</i>
<i>Grantia compressa</i>
<i>Halichondria panicea</i>
<i>Haliclona urceolus</i>
<i>Hymedesmia</i> sp.
<i>Leucosolenia</i> sp.
<i>Polymastia boletiformis</i>
<i>Suberites carnosus</i>
<i>Suberites ficus</i>
<i>Suberities</i> sp.
<i>Sycon ciliatum</i>

PROTECTING THE NORTH SEA: ABERDEENSHIRE

European Headquarters - Madrid

Email: europe@oceana.org

European Union Office - Brussels

Email: brussels@oceana.org

Baltic and North Sea Office - Copenhagen

Email: copenhagen@oceana.org

UK Office - London

Email: oceanauk@oceana.org